

ISSN 2617-2682

Vol. 1, No. 1-2, 2018

International Journal of Science Annals

Key title: International Journal of Science Annals

Abbreviated key title: Int J Sci Ann

Main title: International Journal of Science Annals

Founder and Publisher: Kharkiv Regional

Public Organization "Culture of Health"

(Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH), Ukraine

Publisher's name in the form adopted in the practice

of national cataloging: KRPOCH

Certificate to registration: KB 23195-13035 P, 04.04.2018.

Publishing license: ДК 4387, 10.08.2012.

Publication type: scientific.

Foundation year: 2018.

Frequency: 4 numbers in a year.

Edition Language: English.

Address of Editorial Office and Publisher:

Zabaikalskyi lane, 6, of. 6

Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61105

Tel.: +38 066 239 77 75

Email: ijsa.office@gmail.com

URL: <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org>

Journal is reflected in repositories and databases:

Publons –

<https://publons.com>

Crossref –

<https://www.crossref.org>

Google Scholar –

<http://scholar.google.com>

CORE –

<https://core.ac.uk/join>

Index Copernicus –

<http://journals.indexcopernicus.com>

Scientific Periodicals of Ukraine –

<http://journals.uran.ua>

Scilit –

<https://www.scilit.net/>

V. I. Vernadskiy National Library of Ukraine –

<http://nbuv.gov.ua>

Responsibility for facts, quotations, private names, enterprises and organizations titles, geographical locations etc. to be bared by the authors.

The Editorial Office and Board do not always share the views and thoughts expressed in the articles published.

Full or partial reproduction of articles is allowed, citing to the source and authors.

EDITORIAL BOARD

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Melnyk Yuriy Borysovykh

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogy, Associate Professor, Professor in National Academy of the National Guard of Ukraine, Kharkiv Regional Public Organization "Culture of Health", UKRAINE

SCIENTIFIC EDITORS:

Social Sciences

Vveinhardt Jolita

Doctor of Social Sciences, Professor, Chief Researcher, Vytautas Magnus University, LITHUANIA

Education

Ose Liesma

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Transport and Telecommunication Institute, LATVIA

Psychology

Prykhodko Ihor Ivanovych

Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor, National Academy of the National Guard of Ukraine, UKRAINE

Health Sciences

Wasilewski Bohdan

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, MD, Professor, Psychosomatic Institute, POLAND

EDITORIAL BOARD:

A'Beckett Lyudmilla

Doctor of Sciences, Research Fellow, University of the Free State (South Africa), AUSTRALIA

Ahangar Katayoon

Doctor of Philosophy in Developmental Psychology, University Putra Malaysia, MALAYSIA

Ahmad Nawaz

Doctor of Philosophy, Assistant Professor, Institute of Business Management, PAKISTAN

Bhandari Medani Prasad

Doctor of Philosophy in Sociology, Professor, Akamai University, Hawaii, USA

Bursaitiene Nijole

Doctor of Social Sciences, Professor, Mykolas Romeris University, LITHUANIA

Gonchev Vladimir Hristov

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, MD, Associate Professor, University Assen Zlatarov, BULGARIA

Iskakova Laura Turlibekovna

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Joint stock company "National Center for professional development "Orleu", KAZAKHSTAN

Kaydalova Lidiya Grigorivna

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, National University of Pharmacy, UKRAINE

Kuryk Olena Georhiivna

Doctor of Medical Sciences, MD, Professor, Chief Research Officer, Bogomolets National Medical University, UKRAINE

Manna Reshmi

Doctor of Philosophy in Psychology, Associate Professor, ICFAI Business School-Gurgaon, INDIA

Olefir Valerii Oleksandrovykh

Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Associate Professor, V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, UKRAINE

Oliveira Madalena Sofia

Doctor of Philosophy in Psychology, University Institute of Health Sciences-CESPU, PORTUGAL

Sabra Zizi Elsayed Ibrahim

Doctor of Philosophy in Clinical Psychology, Assistant Professor, Minia University, EGYPT

Sebastiani Ricardo Werner

Doctor of Philosophy in Public Health, Professor, Researcher, Nemeton – Center for Studies and Research in Psychology and Health, BRAZIL

Stadnik Anatoliy Vladimirovich

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Associate Professor, National Academy of the National Guard of Ukraine, UKRAINE

Usakli Hakan

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor, Sinop University, TURKEY

Zarifsanaiey Nahid

Doctor of Philosophy in e-Learning Planning, Associate Professor, Shiraz University of Medical Sciences, IRAN

Zemlianska Olena Volodymyrivna

Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor, Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs, UKRAINE

TECHNICAL EDITOR:

Pypenko Iryna Sergiivna

Doctor of Philosophy in Economics, Associate Professor, Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH, UKRAINE

CONTENTS**ORIGINAL RESEARCH****SOCIAL SCIENCES****Education & Educational Research**

- Melnyk Yu. B., Pypenko I. S.**
Training of Future Specialists in Higher Educational Institutions 4
- Kostina V. V.**
Verification of the System of Preparation of Future Specialists of the Social Sphere
for the Prevention of Maladjustment of Pupils in Various Social Institutions 12
- Usakli H.**
Behavioral Tendencies of Single Parent Students 21

Psychology

- Mitina S. V.**
Empathy in the Structure of Psychological Competence of the Teacher of the
Higher Educational Institution 28

LIFE SCIENCES**Health Care Sciences**

- Prykhodko I. I.**
Program of Psychological Rehabilitation of the National Guard of Ukraine Military Personnel
Participated in Combat Actions 34
- Guidelines for the Authors of International Journal of Science Annals 43

Full-text available free of charge at <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/en/archive>

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Training of Future Specialists in Higher Educational Institutions

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

Melnyk Yu. B.^{1,2 ABCDEFG}, **Pypenko I. S.**^{2,3 ACDE}

¹ National Academy of the National Guard of Ukraine, Ukraine

² Kharkiv Regional Public Organization "Culture of Health" (KRPOCH), Ukraine

³ Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH, Ukraine

Received: 01.08.2018; **Accepted:** 22.08.2018; **Published:** 30.11.2018

Abstract

Background and Aim of Study:

The research deals with studying issues concerning training of specialists in high school and the student's role in this process. The perspective trends of training specialists in higher educational institutions are determined. They relate to such, where the university is a configuration part of much bigger establishments and processes and where it corresponds to the social and individual demands of the youth.

The aim of the study: to ascertain competences, pedagogic technologies and methods, demanded by cadets and students, as well as to forecast perspective trends of studying in higher educational institutions.

Material and Methods:

A set of methods is used to study issues of training specialists in high school: collection of information, systematisation, rating assessment, analysis and results interpretation. The dispersion coefficient of Kendall concordance is calculated, its significance is proved on the basis of determining Pirson's criterion for the significance level of 5% and 1%. The research was held in the academic years of 2013-2018 on the basis of National Academy of National Guard of Ukraine within the framework of the subject "University Education". The average number of respondents was 535 people (35 groups), who studied at the Humanities Faculty, The Technical Faculty, the Faculty of Economics and Management.

Results: *It is specified that there is a tendency of decreasing number of students who want to study in higher educational institutions. The demand of the student youth is determined for competences, pedagogic technologies and methods which are mostly required in high school. It is proposed to specify competences classification and content of the notions "professional competences" and "special competences".*

Conclusions: *On the basis of modern scientific and technical achievements, application of educational logistics and social demand, the main tendencies and future trends of training specialists in higher educational institutions in IT-sphere, technical, military, economic, medical and educational fields are forecast.*

Keywords: *high school, training of specialists, student youth, professional competences, special competences, educational logistics.*

Copyright: © 2018 Melnyk Yu. B., Pypenko I. S. Published by Archives of International Journal of Science Annals

DOI and UDC DOI 10.26697/ijsa.2018.1-2.01; UDC 373.29+355.343::711.57

Conflict of interests: *The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests*

Peer review: *Double-blind review*

Source of support: *Departmental sources*

Information about the authors: **Melnyk Yuriy Borysovych** (Corresponding Author) – <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8527-4638>; YBM.office@gmail.com; Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogy, Associate Professor, Professor of the Department of Psychology and Pedagogy; National Academy of the National Guard of Ukraine; Founder and Chairman of the Board, Kharkiv Regional Public Organization "Culture of Health", Kharkiv, Ukraine.

Pypenko Iryna Sergiivna – <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5083-540X>; edu.center.office@gmail.com; Doctor of Philosophy in Economics, Associate Professor, Director of the Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH; Kharkiv Regional Public Organization "Culture of Health"; Kharkiv, Ukraine.

Introduction

Creating a united European educational system and Ukraine joining the Bologna process demanded a significant renovation in organisation and content of education. The main bases for the higher educational system, declared by a new edition of the law of Ukraine, create conditions for increasing collaboration of state organs and business with higher educational institutions supported by principles of autonomy, combination of education, science and production aimed at training competitive human resources for hi-technological and innovative development of the country, self-realisation of the personality, meeting the needs of the society, labour market and state in qualified workers. In the new edition of the law of Ukraine it is emphasised that training of specialists should be realised with due regard to the needs of a personality, interests of the state, territory communities and employers (Law of Ukraine, 2014).

Thus, the changes in the education paradigm of training specialists, which should be based on collaboration, are declared by standard. Still, as a rule higher education today remains to be organised into strictly specialised spheres of knowledge and traditional subjects that provides training of specialists without taking into account social demand, modern trends and competition at the labour market. That is why it is obvious that such inflexible training of specialists creates a situation when a large part of graduates cannot find a job according to the major obtained in the university. Thus, realising it they refuse from higher education. This problematic situation is highly troubling, as for a developing country it is important to train qualified specialists who can make discoveries, create new products, develop methods and technologies.

There is an urgent necessity to study issues of training qualified specialists in high school which correspond to modern realities and create a reliable basis for employing graduates at the European and world labour market as well as promote personal and professional development of the youth.

Theoretical value and practical significance for developing issues of training qualified workers in high school were implemented in scientific works concerning the problem of organising activity of higher educational institutions in conditions of globalisation and internationalisation (Altbach and Knight, 2007). Institutional dynamics of European University is researched by Olsen (2007). The mission, spheres of training and trends of university activity (mass higher education, professional specialised higher education, research and academic training) are analysed by Laredo (2007). The issues of general management of education quality are revealed in the work by Sallis (2014). The research was realised in the countries of the European Union and was focused on their peculiarities. The realities of the Ukrainian system of higher education and students' requirements into forming their competences in the process of studying in high school differ from the European youth (Melnyk, 2017). Thus, there is a necessity to research the modern system of

students' national training in high school and the student's role in this process.

For the first time an attempt to generalise international and Ukrainian experience as well as to provide methodic recommendations for developing and modernising curricula in conditions of the European integration of national higher education was made by scientists (Zakharchenko, Luhovyi, Rashkevych, and Talanova, 2014).

The content modernisation of curricula required their implementation in high school. It would have been possible on the basis of introducing pedagogic logistics in high school which has an important significance for solving the outlined tasks. The first research into organising the educational process on the grounds of implementing pedagogic logistics in high school has been made by Melnyk and Pypenko (2017), in which the authors proposed methodological and theoretical bases for this activity, determined definitions of the notions: "educational logistics", "pedagogical logistics" and "teaching logistics".

Besides, it was necessary to continue researching and improving the issue of organising psychological and pedagogical interaction in high school. Their theoretical and practical aspects were researched by Melnyk (2017).

The research of the mentioned above issues will give the possibility to organise the educational process of the specific higher educational institution with due regard to the needs of a personality, interests of the state and employers, as well as to provide the modern training of specialists, who will be demanded on the European and international labour market.

The aim of the study. To research issues concerning modern training of specialists in high school and the student's role in this process; to ascertain competences, pedagogic technologies and methods, demanded by cadets and students, as well as to forecast perspective trends of studying in higher educational institutions.

Material and methods

To study the issues of training specialists in high school a set of methods is used:

- collecting information (systematic blind written questionnaires);
- systematisation;
- rating assessment;
- analysis and results interpretation.

The author's methods (questionnaires) and instruments (Melnyk, 2016; 2017) are applied. We were guided by competences classification based on materials of the Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education, QAA, UK and Tuning educational structures in Europe, TUNING (Tuning Association, 2010).

With the aim to determine the concordance level of respondents' ideas, the dispersion coefficient of Kendall concordance has been calculated, its significance (the calculated value of the criterion exceeds the critical one for the significance level of 5% and 1%) has been proved on the basis of Pirson's criterion.

Cadets and students were questioned with due regard to their individual, group and collective choice to provide representative selection and obtain the necessary information.

Participants. 15 groups of cadets and 20 groups of students of the day-time department of National Academy of National Guard of Ukraine (NANGU) have taken part in the research. The average amount of respondents is 535.

Organisation of the research. The research was realised in the academic years of 2013-2018 on the basis of NANGU. In particular, the academic years of 2013-2014 – 3 groups of cadets, 4 groups of students (the average amount of 143 people); the academic years of 2014-2015 – 3 groups of cadets, 4 groups of students (the average amount of 103 people); the academic years of 2015-2016 – 3 groups of cadets, 4 groups of students (the average amount of 105 people); the academic years of 2016-2017 – 3 groups of cadets, 4 groups of students (the average amount of 98 people); the academic years of 2017-2018 – 3 groups of cadets, 4 groups of students (the average amount of 86 people). The cadets and students were questioned around the subject “University education” at the fourth year, of different majors, from the Humanities Faculty, Technical Faculty and the Faculty of Economics and Management.

Statistical analysis. To obtain the rating assessment of the collective selection of students and cadets, the algorithm of calculating the average values has been used, in particular the weighted arithmetic average. The weighted arithmetic average has been calculated from the values of the varying characteristics from 1 to 5 taking into account the weights. Upon that the values of the characteristic are presented in the form of variation distribution series. The quantity of units in the variation series is not the same: 30 competences, 16

technologies, 25 methods. According to each series 5 units have been chosen, that headed the rating. In this case weighting has been carried out by frequencies (weights from 1 to 5), which show how many times this or that variant is repeated. That is why calculating the weighted arithmetic average by each of the chosen competences / technologies / methods all values of the weights in the range from 1 to 5 are multiplied by frequency of their repetition, the obtained cup product has been summed up, this sum has been divided into the sum of frequencies (15), i.e. the average volume of the total. Rank 1 has been assigned to the highest value of the weighted arithmetic average of the corresponding competence / technology / method, rank 5 has been assigned to the lowest one.

The dispersion coefficient of Kendall concordance has been applied to determine the level of concordance of the respondents’ ideas. As there are no connected ranks in the research, the dispersion coefficient of *W* concordance has been calculated as ratio of deviation of the sum of ranks in the second degree from the average sum of ranks in the second degree, multiplied by 12, to the experts quantity *m* in the second degree, multiplied by the spread between the third degree of the quantity of factors which are ranged, and the quantity of these factors *n*.

The obtained value has been estimated in terms of significance with the help of Pirson’s criterion χ^2 by multiplying this coefficient *W* by the quantity of experts *m* and by the quantity of the degrees of clamping (*n*-1). The calculated value of Pirson’s criterion has been compared to the table (critical one).

On this basis the conclusion has been made about the significance of the researched coefficient.

The concordance coefficient and Pirson’s criterion values are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The concordance coefficient and Pirson’s criterion values.

Demand type	The concordance coefficient <i>W</i>	The calculated value of Pirson’s criterion χ^2	The table (critical) value χ^2	
			for the significance level 5%	for the significance level 1%
For demand into competences	0.812	50.02	42.56	49.59
For demand into pedagogic technologies	0.848	33.01	25.00	30.58
For demand into methods	0.873	43.97	36.42	42.98

In all the cases the calculated value of Pirson’s criterion exceeds the table (critical) values for 5% and 1% of the significance level. Thus, the calculated values of the concordance coefficient are accepted as significant that proves the concordance of the respondents’ ideas.

Obtaining the average complex assessment has allowed us to reveal the demand into forming competences / technologies / methods of the student youth for the last five years.

Results

For five years of research (2013-2018 academic years) there has been a tendency to decrease the quantity of cadets and students in groups of the higher educational

institution, who were under research, by 39.86%. If the quantity of students for this period was twice as fewer, then the tendency to decrease the quantity of cadets in groups for the last year (2017-2018) was ceased, and even had a higher index than for the last three years. The results are illustrated in Figure 1.

The demand for forming competences in high school among cadets and students has been studied by methods (Melnyk, 2017), which presuppose individual, group and collective choice of 5 most important competences from the proposed list (30 general competences) (Tuning Association, 2010, p. 63-64). These competences had to be ranged according to the level of their significance.

Figure 1. Dynamics of quantity of student youth in higher educational institution.

The obtained results prove that among cadets and students of NANGU for the last 5 years the most required is the demand into forming the following competences by teachers:

- 1) ability to apply knowledge in practical situations 25.0%;
- 2) determination and perseverance in the tasks given and responsibilities taken 20.7%;
- 3) ability to make reasoned decisions 14.3%;
- 4) ability to work in a team 11.8%;
- 5) ability to adapt and to act in new situation 8.3%;
- 6) all other competences 19.9%.

The demand for other competences has been poorly expressed or is absent at all. Let us note that 12 (40%) out of 30 competences have not been chosen at all. That is why they are not considered in the mathematical calculations. The absence of choice for certain competences indicates the necessity to review the groups classification and their content by other characteristics.

Determining the need for the mentioned above competences, the respondents considered personal needs and possibilities in order to use them in their professional activity.

That is why we consider it to be appropriate to implement such two groups of competences into classification: professional competences and special competences.

Professional competences are general abilities of a personality to perform position duties. They are based on personal skills, knowledge and experience and are revealed in the result of professional activity. For example, professional competences of a teacher are characterised by the indices of their educational and pedagogic, scientific and research, organising and methodic activity.

Special competences are specific abilities of a personality, which are based on their psycho-physiological peculiarities and personal potential as for the possibility to do work defined by the branch standards, where they study or work. For example, special competences of a student are characterised by indices of their academic performance, psycho-social maturity, communication, etc.

The summed up percentage rating of the respondents' questionnaires results for the demand of forming competences in a higher educational institution is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Summed up rating of questionnaire results of student youth for demand into forming competences at higher educational institution.

The carried out research proves that only certain competences are required by the student youth. It can be explained by today's realities and peculiarities of an educational institution. The student youth's demand into forming competences necessary to be mastered by a graduate should be taken into account by teachers when they include them into the content of curricula, as there is a correlation connection between the results of studying and competences (Melnyk, 2017). Studying the demand into forming the student youth competences will favour operational efficiency and flexibility by reacting to their demands.

Questioning cadets and students into their demand for using pedagogic technologies in studies has been carried out by similar methods which presupposed individual, group and collective choice of 5 most

important technologies from the proposed list (16 pedagogic technologies) (Melnyk, 2016, p. 36). These technologies are to be ranged according to the level of their value.

The demand rating for using pedagogic technologies by studying was as follows:

- 1) technologies of distance learning 24.7%;
- 2) technologies of project learning 23.1%;
- 3) technologies of problematic learning 21.3%;
- 4) technologies of programming learning 9.8%;
- 5) technologies of game learning 8.2%;
- 6) all other technologies 12.9%.

The summary rating of the results of the respondents' questionnaires as for the demand into using the pedagogic technologies by studying is shown in percentage in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Summary rating of student youth questionnaires results for demand into using pedagogic technologies in higher educational institution.

The questionnaires results of cadets and students of NANGU for the last 5 years prove that among the most required technologies are those which give them a possibility to be more mobile and provide for acquiring professional competences which guarantee competitiveness at the labour market.

Questioning cadets and students for their demand into using pedagogic methods in high school by the methods mentioned above, presuppose individual, group and collective choice of 5 most important pedagogic methods from the proposed list (25 pedagogic methods) (Melnyk, 2016, p. 27-29). These methods are to be ranged according to the level of their value.

The demand rating for using pedagogic methods by

studying have turned out to be as follows:

- 1) visual methods (illustrations, demonstrations, video watching) 23.2%;
- 2) verbal methods (explanations, clarifications, discussion, dispute) 19.1%;
- 3) practical method (research, exercises under control) 16.7%;
- 4) method case-study (active problematic and situational analysis) 15.9%;
- 5) reproductive method (work by the ready models) 10.8%;
- 6) all other methods 14.3%.

The summary rating of the respondents' questionnaires results for the demand into using pedagogic methods by studying is illustrated in percentage in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Summary rating of students' questionnaires results for demand into using pedagogic methods in high school.

The questionnaires results of cadets and students of NANGU for the last 5 years prove that among the most required methods are those which apply computer and digital equipment, trainers focused on forming competences which provide cadets and students with skills to solve practical tasks. The demand for the first three groups of methods among cadets and students does not differ significantly, while the reproductive method is specific for cadets, and students prefer the method of case-study. It is explained by the peculiarity of military training of cadets at an educational institution. Such methods as working with a book (reviewing, making notes etc.) are practically not chosen by cadets or students. The indices of a verbal method such as story-telling or lecture have turned out to be insignificant.

Discussion

Questioning the student youth has given us a general idea about competences, pedagogic technologies and methods which are among the most demanded in high school. The analysis and systematisation of the research results, as well as the usage of the educational logistics gives the possibility to forecast perspective trends of training specialists at higher educational institutions. In the research we applied the following interpretation of educational logistics and possibilities for its usage in high school: "Educational logistics is a sphere of education that determines the average strategy of its mission, forecasting and development, its specific projecting and planning, forecasting the results as well as determining the standards corresponding to the educational aims" (Melnyk and Pypenko, 2017, p. 13).

Formation of the student youth competences is of vital importance by training future specialists in higher educational institutions. The problems of competences classification in high school are highlighted in the work "Competence-based learning. A proposal for the assessment of generic competences" (Sánchez and Ruiz, 2008). The problem of forming student youth competences in the European educational system is revealed in the materials The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education, QAA, UK and Tuning educational structures in Europe, TUNING (Tuning Association, 2010). The correlation of competences and results of studying in high school are researched by Wagenaar (2014); Burganova, Abdugalina, and Shaiheslyamova (2016). Pedagogic aspects of forming competences of the student youth are researched by Meterbayeva, Karmenbayeva, Tleulinova, Auhadiyeva, and Egimberdieva (2015). Formation of a personality and problems of forming students' competences are revealed in scientific works by Valeeva and Bushmeleva (2016); Melnyk (2017). In the research we applied the classification of competences (Tuning Association, 2010), which consists of three groups: instrumental, interpersonal, system, which in their turn account for the main three dozens of competences. Some of these competences are conventionally referred to a specific group, as they could be found both in the interpersonal and system groups. It has made us

overview this classification and expose a necessity to single out other groups: professional competences and special competences, which are based on another peculiarity, as well as specify the essence of these notions.

The specification proposed by us to the competence classification is not an exchange or reduction of the classification (Tuning Association, 2010). The specification promotes clarification of the group competences content as for the problem of training specialists by specific peculiarities – practical orientation.

Besides, the groups of competences outlined in our research allow classifying their components more substantively in relation to domains as well: self-consciousness, self-administration, social awareness and management of relations (Boyatzis, Goleman, and Rhee, 2000).

It allows determining the specific indices, coordinate syllabi, which will be directed at possibilities of an educational institution, students' request and employers' demand at the European and world labour market.

In the research by Altbach and Knight the modern state of the international education is analysed (Europe, America, Asia, Africa) and the tendencies of increasing demand for international education are outlined, which result in mobility of students and educational institutions through national borders. Also it is forecast "Along with traditional private and public higher education institutions, "new providers" include commercial IT and mediacompanies, corporate universities, professional associations, and international conglomerates. Providers use face-to-face and virtual modes to deliver education to students in their home countries through twinning, franchising, articulation, validation, and joint or double degree arrangements. Some providers also seek to establish a physical presence through branch campuses, independent institutions, teaching and testing centers, and acquisitions or mergers with local higher education institutions" (Altbach and Knight, 2007, p. 295).

Modern scientific and technical achievements, informatisation of the society allow forecasting tendencies and future trends in training specialists in higher educational institutions within the context of distance learning. It requires development of new technologies and methodic provision of the educational process.

Development perspectives of the educational branch within the context of distance learning along with implementation of mobile learning for students is researched by Sahin (2008); Froberg, Goth, and Schwabe (2009); Wang, Shen, Novak, and Pan (2009); Park, (2011); Keegan (2013).

The efficiency and long-term benefits of implementing modern technologies and distance learning are proved: "...innovative 21st strategies make learning in both physical and online classrooms more stimulating and motivating for students, which promote better retention of the course content, minimise dropout rates, and

maximise students' learning of the course content" (Kalaian, 2017).

The research by Schmidt, Baran, Thompson, Mishra, Koehler, and Shin (2009) is useful for description and comprehension of goals by using technologies in the educational sphere Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK). The possibilities of managing technologies of teaching and studying in high school are revealed by Bates A., Bates T., and Sangra (2011). The perspectives and problems of teaching structures in higher education of Europe are researched by Haug (1999). Teaching methods in high school have been a core subject of numerous research for many years (Wiersma and Jurs, 2005; Lodico, Spaulding, and Voegtle, 2010).

In their work Wiersma and Jurs (2005) give a general idea for using methods of the research in education, pay attention to quantitative and qualitative indices as well as methods of statistics as important research tools.

The fact that cadets and students chose mentioned above technologies and methods that involve modern IT-technologies and distance learning was easy to foresee. However the choice of case-study and reproductive methods has to be explained.

Choosing the method of case-study (active problematic and situational analysis) was specific mainly for students, and more seldom for cadets, who studied at the Technical Faculty and the Faculty of Economics and Management. We relate the student youth's interest in the real fact material and solving problematic situations close to the reality, to their need of forming professional and special competences, which will help them in practical activity.

The reproductive method (work by ready patterns) has been chosen by cadets and students of the Humanities Faculty. We explain it by the trend of training and peculiarity (military one) of the educational institution. Thus, we relate the choice of these 5 methods among others which have been proposed to the respondents (cadets and students), firstly – to the social demand of the student youth into forming professional and special competences in high school, which correspond to the modern realities; secondly – to the field of training; thirdly – to the peculiarity of the educational institution. That is why developing technological and methodical support of a higher educational institution, administration and teachers have to take into account such factors as peculiarities of an educational institution, social requests of the student youth for competences and employers' demand for them.

Conclusions

It has become of vital importance for training specialists in high school to study the problem of determining competences, pedagogic technologies and methods required by the student youth as well as specifying the tendencies of developing the branch in which the educational services are provided. On the grounds of modern scientific and technical achievements, educational logistics and social demand we forecast the following basic tendencies and

perspective trends in training specialists in higher educational institutions:

- 1) IT-sphere (programming, design, analytics);
- 2) technical and military spheres (engineering, robot technology);
- 3) economic branch (trading of alternative currencies, cryptographic finance);
- 4) medical branch (genetics, transplantology, bioengineering, molecular dietology);
- 5) educational branch (mobile learning in the context of distance education).

Taking into account perspective trends in training specialists will allow higher educational institutions to elaborate the development strategy of their institution and the content of syllabi according to the modern tendencies. It will have a positive influence on the quantity of students who will be able to get education for a Bachelor's degree as well as to continue it by Master's or Post-graduate programme, and also courses for retraining specialists. By such conditions the university will be able to provide their main function, i.e. training highly qualified specialists, and will be smoothly integrated as a configuration part of much bigger establishments and processes, into the national and European educational sphere, providing for social and individual needs of the youth. There is a necessity to study further the issues of competences classification as well as content development of group components "professional competences" and "special competences" according to the syllabi of training specialists at different levels of higher education.

Funding source

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors. It has been conducted on the basis of National Academy of National Guard of Ukraine within the framework of the subject "University Education".

References

- Altbach, Ph. G., & Knight, J. (2007). The internationalization of higher education: motivations and realities. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 11, 290–305. doi:10.1177/1028315307303542
- Bates, A. W., Bates, T., & Sangra, A. (2011). *Managing technology in higher education: Strategies for transforming teaching and learning*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Boyatzis, R., Goleman, D., & Rhee, K. (2000). *Clustering competence in emotional intelligence: Insights from the Emotional Competence Inventory (ECI)*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Burganova, R. I., Abdugalina, S. E., & Shaiheslyamova, K. O. (2016). The professional competence formation in the training process in higher educational institution. *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 11(10), 3629-3639.
- Frohberg, D., Goth, C., & Schwabe, G. (2009). Mobile learning projects: a critical analysis of the state of the art. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 25, 307-331.
- Haug, G. (1999). Trends and issues in learning structures in higher education in Europe. In G. Haug, & J. Kirstein [Eds.], *EUA Trends and learning structures in higher*

- education reports series* (pp. 3-18). Retrieved from http://www.aic.lv/ace/ace_disk/acebook/Trends_all.pdf
- Kalaian, S. A. (2017). Pedagogical approaches for the 21st century student-driven learning in STEM classrooms. In N. Alias, & J. Luanan (Eds.), *Student-Driven Learning Strategies for the 21st Century Classroom* (pp. 72–86). Hershey, PA: IGI Global. doi:10.4018/978-1-5225-1689-7.ch006
- Keegan, D. (2013). *Foundations of distance education*. London: Routledge.
- Laredo, P. (2007). Revisiting the Third Mission of Universities: Toward a Renewed Categorization of University Activities? *Higher Education Policy*, 20(4), 441–456.
- Lodico, M. G., Spaulding, D. T., & Voegtle, K. H. (2010). *Methods in educational research: From theory to practice*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Melnyk, Yu. B. (2016). *Pedahohika vyshchoi shkoly: v skhemakh i tablytsiakh* [High school pedagogy: in charts and tables]. Kharkiv: KRPOCH. doi:10.26697/9789669726063.2016 [in Ukrainian]
- Melnyk, Yu. (2017). Study of trends of students' demand for the formation of competences by higher educational institutions. *Science and Education*, 5, 128–134. doi:10.24195/2414-4665-2017-5-22
- Melnyk, Yu. B., & Pypenko, I. S. (2017). Sutnist i vzaiemozviazok poniat "osvitnia lohistryka", "pedahohichna lohistryka" ta "navchalna lohistryka" [The essence and interrelation of the concepts "educational logistics", "pedagogical logistics" and "teaching logistics"]. In L. M. Pelepeychenko, & Yu. B. Melnyk (Eds.), *Aktualni pytannia osvity i nauky – Current issues of education and science* (pp. 9–17). Kharkiv: KRPOCH. doi:10.26697/9786177089000.2017.9 [in Ukrainian]
- Melnyk, Yu. B. (2017). Rekomendatsii do reitynhovoho otsiniuvannia naukovo-pedahohichnykh pratsivnykiv [Recommendations for rating assessment of scientific and pedagogical workers]. In T. V. Kolbina, & Yu. B. Melnyk (Eds.), *Psykhologo-pedahohichni problemy stanovlennia suchasnoho fakhivtsia – Psychological and pedagogical problems of modern specialist formation* (pp. 92–98). Kharkiv: KRPOCH. doi:10.26697/9789669726087.2017.92 [in Ukrainian]
- Meterbayeva, K., Karmenbayeva, Zh., Tleulinova, M., Auhadieva, Z., & Egimberdieva, G. (2015). Pedagogical bases of professional competence formation of the future specialists. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 185, 240–243. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.03.465
- Olsen, J. P. (2007). The institutional dynamics of the European University. In P. Maassen, & J. Olsen (Eds.), *University Dynamics and European Integration* (pp. 25–54). Luxembourg: Springer. doi:10.1007/978-1-4020-5971-1
- Park, Y. (2011). A pedagogical framework for mobile learning: categorizing educational applications of mobile technologies into four types. *International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 12(2), 78–102.
- Sahin, S. (2008). The relationship between student characteristics including learning styles, and their perceptions and satisfaction in web-based courses in higher education. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 9(1), 123–138.
- Sallis, E. (2014). *Total quality management in education* (3rd ed.). London: Taylor and Francis.
- Sánchez, A. V., & Ruiz, M. P. (Eds.). (2008). *Competence-based learning. A proposal for the assessment of generic competences*. Bilbao: University of Deusto.
- Schmidt, D. A., Baran, E., Thompson, A. D., Mishra, P., Koehler, M. J., & Shin, T. S. (2009). Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK): The development and validation of an assessment instrument for preservice teachers. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 42(2), 123–149. doi:10.1080/15391523.2009.10782544
- Tuning Association. (2010). *A tuning guide to formulating degree programme profiles including programme competences and programme learning outcomes*. Bilbao: Groningen and The Hague. Retrieved from http://www.unideusto.org/tuningeu/images/stories/documents/Tuning_Guide_Degree_programme_profile_s.pdf.
- Valeeva, R. A., & Bushmeleva, N. A. (2016). Forming analytical competency of higher school students. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 11(8), 3137-3148. Retrieved from <http://www.iejme.com/makale/925>.
- Wagenaar, R. (2014). Competences and learning outcomes: a panacea for understanding the (new) role of Higher Education? *Tuning Journal for Higher Education: Competence-based learning: a global perspective*, 1(2), 279–302. doi:10.18543/tjhe-1(2)-2014pp279-302
- Wang, M., Shen, R., Novak, D., & Pan, X. (2009). The impact of mobile learning on students' learning behaviours and performance: Report from a large blended classroom. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 40(4), 673–695.
- Wiersma, W., & Jurs, S. G. (2005). *Research methods in education: An introduction* (9th ed.). Cambridge: Pearson.
- Zakharchenko, V. M., Luhovyi, V. I., Rashkevych, Yu. M., & Talanova, Zh. V. (2014). *Rozroblennia osvitnikh prohram* [Development of educational programs]. Kyiv: DP "NVTs "Priorytety". [in Ukrainian]
- Zakon Ukrainy "Pro vyshchu osvitu": pryiniaty 1 lyp. 2014 roku № 1556-VII [Law of Ukraine "On higher education" from July 1 2014, № 1556-VII]. (2014, August 6). *Holos Ukrainy – Voice of Ukraine*, 148, pp. 4-67. [in Ukrainian]

Cite this article as:

Melnyk, Yu. B., & Pypenko, I. S. (2018). Training of future specialists in higher education institutions. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 1(1-2), 4–11. doi:10.26697/ijsa.2018.1-2.01

The electronic version of this article is the complete one and can be found online at: <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/en/archive>

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>).

Verification of the System of Preparation of Future Specialists of the Social Sphere for the Prevention of Maladjustment of Pupils in Various Social Institutions

Author's Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

Kostina V. V.¹ ABCDEFG

¹ H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Ukraine

Received: 20.08.2018; Accepted: 15.09.2018; Published: 30.11.2018

Abstract

Background and Aim of Study:

The article is devoted to the problem of professional preparation of specialists in the social sphere.

The aim of the study: to describe the structure of conducting a pedagogical experiment on the research problem and determine its qualitative results.

Material and Methods:

During the implementation of the pilot study to determine the effectiveness of the the impact, made by developed system of training future specialists in the social sphere to prevent the maladjustment of pupils, on their professional competence, methods of comparing, analyzing and generalizing the results of the process of professional education in the control and experimental groups were used.

Results:

The logical structure of conducting an experimental research on the training of future social pedagogues and social workers for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils, which envisaged the implementation of five consecutive stages and methodological support for its implementation, as well as a system of criteria (motivational and value-based, affective-conative, cognitive-instrumental and professional activity competencies) and corresponding indicators (interest and need of prevention of maladjustment of pupils; professional worldview as the basis for the development of professional culture, characteristics of temperament and will, that are ensuring the successful implementation of prevention of maladjustment of pupils; personal qualities necessary for working with vulnerable contingents, general-pedagogical potential, developed social intelligence, knowledge of the organization of socio-pedagogical and social activities of prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions; knowledge of the technological basis for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils; professional knowledge and skills in the prevention of maladjustment of pupils; experience in social-pedagogical and social preventive work).

Conclusions:

Qualitative changes in personal and professional characteristics of future specialists of the social sphere are determined in accordance with the presented criteria system after the implementation of the forming part of the study.

Keywords:

training, specialists in the social sphere, prevention of maladjustment of pupils, social institutions, system of preparation of future specialists of the social sphere.

Copyright:

© 2018 Kostina V. V. Published by Archives of International Journal of Science Annals

DOI and UDC

DOI 10.26697/ijasa.2018.1-2.02; UDC 378.147.013.42

Conflict of interests:

The author declares that there is no conflict of interests

Peer review:

Double-blind review

Source of support:

Departmental sources

Information about the author:

Kostina Valentyna Viktorivna (Corresponding Author) – <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2410-7497>; Vkostina2014@gmail.com; Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogy, Associate Professor, Doctorant of the Department of Pre-school, Primary School and Professional Education; H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University; Kharkiv, Ukraine.

Introduction

Analysis of scientific literature on the problem of determining the effectiveness of experimental research on the professional training of specialists in the social sphere (Bezpalko, 2015; Bogdanova, 2016; Vainola, 2009; Grinyova, 2014; Grishchenko, 2011; Gurenko, 2013; Zvereva, 2013; Kapska, 2010; Karpenko, 2007; Myshchik, 1997; Polischuk, 2011; Teslenko, 2007; Kharchenko, 2006, etc.) showed that the necessity of distinguishing the logical sequence of it and the selection of clear methodological support at all its stages was substantiated by the scientists.

On the basis of the generalization of the ideas of scientists (Goncharenko, 2010; Kiveryalg, 1980; Kraevskii, 2001; Yadov, 2007), it was determined that among the important conditions for the effective implementation of experimental research is its validity, representativeness, reproducibility, systemicity and optimality in choosing methods and tools. Taking into account the foregoing, in order to ensure the effectiveness of the pedagogical experiment, we have identified a certain logical structure of the experiment.

The aim of the study. To describe the structure of conducting a pedagogical experiment on the problem of professional training of future social pedagogues and social workers for prevention of maladjustment of pupils and determine its qualitative results.

Material and methods

In order to test the hypothesis of the study on the effectiveness of the developed system of professional training of future social pedagogues and social workers for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils from 2011 to 2018, a scientific and pedagogical experiment was conducted on the basis of the H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, A. S. Makarenko Sumy State Pedagogical University, Kryvyi Rih State Pedagogical University, and social institutions of the partner university of higher education network (Kharkiv secondary school No 36, Kharkiv gymnasium No 43, Kharkiv specialized secondary school No 134, CSSSDM of Kyiv and Kholodnogorsk districts, Kharkiv regional center of social & psychological rehabilitation and Kharkiv regional children's center of social psychological rehabilitation "Harmony", social services of the charitable organization "Charitable Foundation "Caritas-Kharkiv" and charitable organization "Kharkiv Charitable Foundation "Blago", Kharkiv regional public organization "Health Culture").

Experimental work was based on the assumption that the modeling and implementation of the system of training future specialists in the social sphere to prevent maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions in a professionally-oriented educational space would ensure the professional readiness of future specialists in the social sphere (social pedagogues and social workers) to the corresponding kind of professional activity, where leading components would be competencies such as motivational and value-based, affective-conative, cognitive-instrumental, professional activity-based.

Research and experimental work were carried out in several stages, each of which provided for specific tasks to obtain data for further processing.

In the first stage (2010-2011), a search portion of the experiment was conducted. During this period the problem of prevention of pupils' maladjustment was studied as a phenomenon of social-pedagogical science and practice of social work, the peculiarities of their use in the system of professional training of future specialists of social sphere were studied and the initial theoretical principles of the research were specified.

During the pilot part of the experiment, the following activities were carried out:

1. Study of the attitude of teachers and students of the specialty "Social pedagogy" to the problem of preventing maladjustment of pupils.
2. Identification of the opportunities of the partner network of institutions in relation to the implementation of the professional training of specialists to the specified type of activity.
3. Diagnosis of the level of formation in specialists of the social sphere of preparedness for the implementation of prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions. Diagnostic tools of this part of the experiment consisted of methods of observation, interviews, questionnaires, oral questioning, document analysis.

In the second stage (2012-2013) a theoretical analysis of literary sources on the problem of training future specialists in the social sphere for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils was conducted, there was systematized and generalized the scientific and pedagogical experience of implementing the professional education of future social pedagogues and social workers to the appropriate kind of professional activity, scientific assumptions were formed, further study of the research problem continued. At this time, the task of the study, its concept, working hypothesis were formulated, the toolkit for the experiment was developed. For this part of the study, theoretical methods of research (analysis, synthesis, comparison, abstraction, generalization, modeling) were widely used.

At the third stage of the research (2013-2014), the qualitative part of the experimental study was conducted, during which the initial level of formation of professional competence of future social pedagogues and social workers for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils was determined. The diagnosis of the level of formation in future specialists of the social sphere of preparedness for the implementation of the prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions at the beginning of the experiment, was conducted using such tools as observation methods, interviews, questionnaires, oral questioning, testing, document analysis, and mathematical statistics. To perform diagnosis of the formation of the readiness of future specialists of the social sphere to prevent the maladjustment of pupils, were used the following criteria and markers: motivational and value-based (interest and need to work on prevention of

maladjustment of pupils, professional outlook), affective-conative (features of temperament and will, personal qualities needed to work with vulnerable contingents), cognitive-instrumental (general pedagogical potential, social intelligence; knowledge of the organization of socio-pedagogical and social activities for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions; knowledge of the technological basis for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils) and professional activity-based (professional knowledge and skills for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils; experience of social-pedagogical and social preventive work). On this basis, four levels of formation of the readiness of future social pedagogues and social workers to prevent maladjustment of pupils were identified (Kostina, 2017, pp. 13-16): insufficient, primary, professionally-qualified, professionally-specialized. The determination of these levels is given in Table 1 and the control and experimental groups are selected.

In the fourth stage (2013-2017), the forming and control parts of the experiment were conducted. During this period, a system of professional training for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils was introduced into the process of professional education of future social pedagogues and social workers. The formative stage of the experiment was carried out on the basis of the H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University.

Students of specialties "Social pedagogy" and "Social work" took part in it. Among the methods of research at this stage, the pedagogical experiment, for which the scientific and methodical tools developed during the course of work were used, as well as the diagnostic methods by which the diagnostics and analysis of the formation of readiness of future social pedagogues and social workers were carried out, was determined to be the the main one.

Among the theoretical methods used at this stage of the study were analysis, grouping, synthesis, comparison, induction, deduction. The statistical analysis of the results of the study was based on the non-parametric Pearson's criterion χ^2 .

The probability and validity of experimental data was provided through the use of standardized techniques and the organization of the experiment in the real educational process of educational institutions and social assistance institutions of the partner network of higher educational establishments.

During the fifth stage (2017-2018), the processing and analysis of the results of the pedagogical experiment with the wording on this basis of relevant conclusions was carried out, the dissertation work was completed and the prospects for further research of the problem of training of future specialists of the social sphere for prevention of maladjustment of pupils were determined. Among the main methods used at this stage were comparison, analysis, grouping, synthesis, deduction, induction.

Results

During the pilot part of the study, we conducted an oral and written survey of social specialists working in

educational and social assistance institutions with students who are prone to maladjustment. The data obtained allowed us to determine that most specialists (70.2%) noted that during work with vulnerable contingents (maladjusted pupils, their parents or those who replace them) have many difficulties, and teachers and educators of such children need help, they often (65.0%) are not fully prepared for the organization of the social-educational environment for such children, and most specialists have a desire to take the necessary training course (70.2%), which confirmed the need to improve the efficiency of the process of training future social pedagogues and social workers in implementing prevention of maladjustment of pupils.

When asked a question "Please assess your own readiness to create a social and educational environment for maladjusted pupils in the social institution where you work", the majority of respondents (52.6%) answered that they were half ready for the corresponding professional job, while others (47.4%) showed even less readiness for this type of activity. And the question "about the importance of implementing comprehensive preventive activities" 37.0% of respondents answered affirmatively. To the question "Would you like to pass the special course "Prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions", 61.4% answered – yes, will do so with pleasure; 26.3% - yes, if my superiors will give me an opportunity, which confirms the need for professional training of specialists to the appropriate type of activity.

In order to conduct a pedagogical experiment on checking the hypothesis in relation to determining the effectiveness of the developed system of professional training of future specialists in the social sphere for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils, we conducted a qualitative part of the study, during which we ran diagnostics against a contingent of students - future specialists of the social sphere, of the H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Kryvyi Rih State Pedagogical University, A. S. Makarenko Sumy State Pedagogical University, and we also selected the contingent of participants in the experiment (control and experimental groups), which at the beginning of the formative stage of the experimental study almost did not differ according to the criteria and indices of the research, as defined in Table 1.

According to Karpenko (2007, p. 206), based on the content of the State Standard in the field of social work, "the process of professional development includes five stages: 1) introduction (the formation of personal intentions, the conscious choice of the profession, taking into account psychological peculiarities); 2) professional training (formation of professional orientation of the system of knowledge, skills and abilities, mastering the experience of solving professional problems and situations); 3) professional adaptation (conscious admission to the profession, mastering the new social role, professional self-determination, mastering the experience of independent performance of professional activities in different directions and needs of the social sphere);

Table 1. Criteria, indicators and levels of readiness of future social pedagogues and social workers to prevent maladjustment of pupils.

Readiness components	Readiness criteria	Readiness indicators	Readiness levels
Personal potential	Motivations and values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interest and need for prevention of maladjustment of pupils; - Professional outlook as the basis for development of professional culture. 	<p>1) insufficient (the future specialist does not have motivation and interest in the prevention of maladjustment of pupils, has poorly developed professional outlook (undeveloped professional ideals, values, lack of professional beliefs);</p> <p>2) primary (the future specialist has poorly developed motivation and there is only an occasional interest in preventing maladjustment of pupils, poorly developed professional outlook (unclear professional ideals, values, unconscious professional beliefs);</p> <p>3) professionally-qualificational (the future specialist has sufficiently developed motivation and interest in the prevention of maladjustment of pupils, developed professional outlook (realized professional ideals and values);</p> <p>4) professional-specialized (the future specialist is highly motivated and interested in the implementation of activities and research on the prevention of maladjustment of pupils, a fully developed professional worldview (available professional ideals, values and professional beliefs).</p>
	Affective-conative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The peculiarities of temperament and will, which ensure the successful implementation of the prevention of maladjustment of pupils; - Personal qualities needed to work with vulnerable contingents 	<p>1) insufficient (future specialist has no volitional qualities that result in the manifestation of adequate professionally-required behavior in conditions of interaction with vulnerable contingents, also has low indicators of stress resistance, empathy and other personality traits);</p> <p>2) primary (future specialist has weakly developed volitional qualities that determine the manifestation of adequate professional behavior in the context of interaction with vulnerable contingents, not fully developed stress resistance, empathy, ability to reflect and facilitation);</p> <p>3) professionally-qualificational (the future specialist has sufficiently developed volitional qualities that determine the manifestation of adequate professional behavior in the context of interaction with vulnerable contingents; fully developed humanity, benevolence, tolerance, stress resistance, empathy and ability to reflect, facilitation);</p> <p>4) professional-specialized (the future specialist has high indicators of the development of volitional qualities that determine the manifestation of adequate professional behavior in the context of interaction with vulnerable contingents, fully developed humanity, benevolence, tolerance, creativity, stress resistance, empathy, ability to reflect and facilitation, the student demonstrates the ability to manage own behavior and positively influence the behavior of others).</p>
Professional potential	Cognitive-instrumental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General pedagogical potential; - Developed social intelligence; - Knowledge of the organization of socio-pedagogical and social activities for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions; - Knowledge of the technological basis of implementation of prevention of maladjustment of pupils 	<p>1) insufficient (future specialist has no general pedagogical potential and knowledge on prevention of maladjustment of pupils and implementation of technologies and methods of work in that direction, underdeveloped social intelligence (missing pro-social orientation of the individual, very low self-efficacy, absent empathic interest and attitude of seeing value in others);</p> <p>2) primary (future specialist has poorly developed general pedagogical potential and knowledge system for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils and technological bases of work in the indicated direction, they are fragmented, there is poorly developed social intelligence (almost missing expressed pro-social orientation of the individual, low self-efficacy, almost absent empathic interest and attitude of seeing value in others);</p> <p>3) professionally-qualificational (the future specialist has fully developed general pedagogical potential and knowledge on the prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions and the application of technologies and methods of work in this direction in various social institutions, sufficiently developed social intelligence (expressed pro-social orientation of personality, high self-efficacy, possesses empathic interest and attitude of seeing value in others);</p> <p>4) professional-specialized (the future specialist has fully developed general-pedagogical potential and system of knowledge on the prevention of maladjustment of pupils and application of technologies and methods of work in this direction in various social institutions, he or she demonstrates knowledge of system-forming links between them and interest to conduct analysis of research prevention of maladjustment of pupils).</p>
	Professional activity-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professional skills and skills in the prevention of maladjustment of pupils (gnostic; predictive; designing; organizing communicative; evaluating); - Experience in social-pedagogical and social prevention work. 	<p>1) insufficient (the future specialist has poorly developed individual professional skills in the prevention of maladjustment of pupils in different social institutions; there is no experience of volunteer initiatives and practices for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils in different social institutions);</p> <p>2) primary (the future specialist has a poorly developed system of professional skills for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions; there is a fragmentary experience of preventing maladjustment of pupils in different social institutions during educational practices);</p> <p>3) professionally-qualificational (the future specialist has a fully developed system of professional skills for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions; possesses volunteer experience and experience in preventing maladjustment of pupils in different social institutions during educational and hands-on practices);</p> <p>4) professional-specialized (the future specialist has fully developed system of professional skills for preventing maladjustment of pupils in different social institutions, there exists volunteering experience, successful completion of practical work, as well as professional experience in preventing maladjustment of pupils in different social institutions while working in a position of social pedagogue or social worker).</p>

4) professionalization (formation of a professional position, integration of personal and professional qualities and skills in stable professionally meaningful education, qualified performance of professional activity); 5) professional mastery (full, multifaceted realization of personality in professional activity on the basis of integrated psychological and pedagogical formations)".

Taking into account the above, with the aim of creating a system of professional training of future specialists in the social sphere to prevent maladjustment of pupils, during the organization of the formative stage of the study, we have identified such important components, scientific and methodological support, in accordance with the model of developed by us system of professional training (Kostina, 2018, pp. 176-177), the introduction of which in the educational process of higher educational institutions contributed to the creation of a professionally oriented educational space, which ensures increased efficiency of professional readiness of specialists for conducting the appropriate type of professional activity: 1) to create the conditions for effective introduction of future professionals in prevention of maladjustment of pupils, in different social institutions has been introduced the work of the volunteer group within the Student Scientific Society (SSS); 2) in order to increase the effectiveness of the students' professional training, a workshop is organized at various social institutions as well as during the training of future social pedagogues and social workers, with the introduction of elements of personality-oriented developmental techniques within the main disciplines of professional training and corresponding special courses; 3) in order to improve the quality of professional adaptation of future social pedagogues and social workers in the process of research activities, an educational and developmental environment for the work of SSS in the conditions of higher educational establishments and at the bases of the affiliate network has been created; 4) for the successful professionalization of future specialists in the social sphere, conditions have been created for the gradual growth of social and personal activity of students in social and project volunteering activities; 5) enrichment of the elements of reflective and creative environments during study with the use of ethno-pedagogical means and animation activities (use of folklore, means of theatricalization, artistic creativity, etc.), which provide activation of the creative potential of future specialists and encourage them to find their own professional style and increase pedagogical skill.

According to the above-mentioned stages of formation of the professional readiness of future specialists of the social sphere for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils, we determined certain tasks, forms and methods that were used at each of those stages during the pilot study (see Table 2).

The process of professional introduction among students of experimental groups was conducted by involving them in a supportive educational and professional space with the participation of senior students who are active members of the SSS and the

participants of the volunteer group work.

At the end of each September, the social-educational event "Welcome to Freshmen" is organized, during which they had an opportunity in warm atmosphere to get acquainted with the best achievements of students and teachers of specialties "Social pedagogy" and "Social work" of senior years of study, with opportunities of professional and personal growth in teaching and extracurricular activities, traditions and important events in the life of the Department of Social Pedagogy and the Faculty of Psychology and Sociology of Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, and also feel like part of a large family of future social pedagogues, social workers.

During this meeting, close mentor-like relations are established between the first-year students and the Master's Degree students of the fifth year of study - active participants of the SSS, who from that moment on begin a conscientious and responsible work to involve them in the work of the SSS first as volunteers, and then, gradually including them in active scientific activity. Starting from this day, the SSS activists conduct meticulous work in extracurricular time with all first-year students, and, based on their own experience in writing scientific research papers and the provisions on holding a competition "Freshmen's Scientific Debut", gradually choose the capable ones and prepare them for participation in the corresponding general university competition, creating conditions for effective professional choice, as well as developing their own personal and professional potential in the indicated direction.

The organization and holding of the "Freshmen's Scientific Debut" competition is the next stage in creating the conditions for ensuring a positive professional choice of future specialists in the social sphere, as well as one of the stages of obtaining professional skills for students of the fifth and sixth years of study, as they have to organize and hold it. All first-year students take part in the competition, but depending on their own abilities and desires, could perform in different roles: the speaker announcing the results of scientific research at the competition (students who are most capable of scientific activity); speaker support group (students developing their own professional opportunities for teamwork and facilitation support); students-observers (students who are not yet active in scientific professional activities, but are trained on the example of others).

Furthermore, during the study year, first-year students are actively involved with the SSS leaders who are part of the volunteer group, to carry out various social and educational preventive measures in various social institutions of the partner network as volunteers (general educational institutions, etc.). In carrying out volunteer initiatives, future specialists in the social sphere have the opportunity to see in practice what the essence of social and educational interaction is, which important characteristics determine the success of its implementation, which helps them to more consciously enter the environment of professional interaction, finding their own reserves and opportunities.

Table 2. Stages and methods of experimental research on the formation of the professional readiness of future social pedagogues and social workers to prevent maladjustment of pupils.

Stages	Tasks	Forms, methods
Introduction	Formation of personal intentions in relation to future professionalisation in the direction of prevention of maladjustment of pupils, conscious choice of the appropriate professional orientation taking into account their own psychological peculiarities	The work of the volunteer group within the SSS, involving future specialists in social and educational activities, the educational work of the faculty and specialty (scientific and creative contests "Freshmen's Scientific Debut", educational events "Welcome to Freshmen", "The initiation of freshmen into social workers")
Professional training	Formation of a professionally-oriented system of knowledge, skills and abilities in relation to the essence and features of the prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions, mastering the experience of solving professional problems and situations in the specified direction of professional activity	Introduction of elements of personality-oriented developmental techniques within the main disciplines of professional training and corresponding special courses, as well as during the practice in various social services
Professional adaptation	A conscious assimilation of the professional duties of a social pedagogue and a social worker of a certain social institution during practice in the context of preventive work with pupils, mastering a new social role, professional self-determination in the direction of prevention of maladjustment of pupils, mastering the experience of self-fulfilling professional activities to prevent maladjustment of pupils in different institutions of the social sphere	Training course "Practical readiness of future specialists of the social sphere for preventive work with vulnerable contingents" during the practice in the educational institutions and social services; Creation of an educational and developing environment for the future specialists of the social sphere in the conditions of higher educational establishments and at the bases of the partner network; provision of opportunities for carrying out of scientific social-pedagogical research on bases of the partnership with the higher educational establishments of the network
Professionalization	Formation of a professional position in relation to the coordination role of a specialist in the social sphere in the prevention of maladjustment of pupils, the integration of personal and professional qualities and skills in stable professional education, providing skilled performance of professional activities in the comprehensive prevention of maladjustment of pupils	Ensuring permanent work of the volunteer group of future social pedagogues and social workers, which plans and implements social and educational preventive measures in various social institutions of the partner network and creates conditions for the gradual growth of social and personal activity of students in social and preventive volunteering activities
Mastery of profession	Full, multifaceted realization of the potential of the personality of the future specialist of the social sphere in the professional activity on the prevention of maladjustment of pupils on the basis of the formation of his personal (motivational & value-based, affective-conative) and professional (cognitive-instrumental and professional activity) competency to the specified type of activity	Ensuring the operation of SSS: organization and conducting of social and educational work at the bases of practice (secondary school No 36, secondary school No 134, secondary school No 156, Gymnasium No 43, Gymnasium No 169, social services of the partner network); organization and conducting of partnership interaction with students and scientific and pedagogical workers of social sphere within the framework of annual joint scientific seminar in Kharkiv Humanitarian and Pedagogical Academy; Organization and conducting of the annual inter-university student's scientific conference "Actual problems of research in the field of social pedagogy and social work" in H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University

The final stage of the organization of the process of professional inclusion of future specialists in the social sphere is "Initiation of Freshmen into Social Workers", carried out by Master's Degree students in the spring, during the annual student's scientific and practical conference "Actual problems of research in the field of social pedagogy and social work".

The next stage of professional development of future specialists in the social sphere is the professional training that was carried out in experimental groups and provided for examination of the effectiveness of the developed methodological support, the main elements of which were: general-professional preparation for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils (supplementing the professional disciplines of the training of future social pedagogues and social workers); special training of future specialists in the social sphere to work on the prevention of maladjustment in various social institutions (introduction of special courses "Guardianship and Care", "Designing the social and educational environment for children and youth organizations", "Ethnopedagogy", "Social work for the formation of a

healthy lifestyle").

An important component of the training of future professionals in the social sphere for prevention of maladjustment of pupils is organization of a training workshop for first- and second-year students, during which they visit social institutions of the partner network (center of social services for families, children and youth (CSSFCY), centers for social and psychological rehabilitation for children, special education centers, family-type orphanages, probation services, etc.) in order to get acquainted with the specifics of the social work of the institutions involved in the prevention of maladjustment of children and young people.

In order to create conditions for the professional adaptation of future specialists to performing professional tasks in a certain social institution, the organization of training and hands-on practices at CSSFCY and secondary schools during third and fourth years of university study is organized, during which students have an opportunity to get acquainted with the essence and specifics of the work of a social worker and a social pedagogue, who coordinates the

activities of certain social institution for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils.

In order to become more aware of the entry into the professional world of specialists in the social sphere, students undergo a training course "Practical readiness of future specialists of the social sphere for preventive work with vulnerable contingents" within the framework of hands-on practice in the educational institutions and social services, during which, with the help of qualified methodologists that are working in the social sphere, they have the opportunity to find out their level of personal readiness for the implementation of preventive activities, get acquainted with the problems and difficulties of socialization which arise in children and young people and learn effective forms, methods, means and methods of professional preventive activities with pupils.

During the practice, students learn the experience of methodologists of the partner network of institutions, on the basis of generalization of which they have to independently prepare and implement several social and educational preventive measures with the involvement of specialists of social services and resources of the institution where they are trained. Also, at the bases of practice of the affiliate network of institutions, students - future social pedagogues and social workers, have the opportunity to organize and conduct activities within their own research, not limited to their own practice, which also contributes to a more effective social adaptation to a particular type of professional activity.

To ensure the effective passing of professional adaptation trials, it is necessary to create conditions for the continuous professional activity of future specialists to increase their social activity and creativity. To this end, senior students who are active members of the SSS are involved in the organization and conduct of various volunteer initiatives within the university and various social institutions of the city, as coordinators. This work enables future social pedagogues and social workers to determine their own reserves and resources, which contributes to a more informed assimilation of the learning information during senior years of study and prevents the development of professional burnout by future professionals who are constantly enriching their personal and professional resources, widening the circle of their own professional interaction.

In order to create conditions for the development of professional skills of future social pedagogues and social workers in the conditions of the work of the SSS, the organization and thematic meetings of the scientific student society was introduced, during which senior students that are active members of the SSS, who are winners of the All-Ukrainian Olympiads, tournaments and contests in specialties "Social pedagogy" and "Social work" have the opportunity to prepare and hold a meeting of a scientific circle on a certain topic that is the subject of their own science research and familiarize junior students with its theoretical and practical aspects and share their practical skills in social work within a particular issue, while implementing their own master class. During the

meetings of the scientific circle for the purpose of exchange of experience, leading experts of social services of the partner network of higher educational establishments, which introduce innovative methods and technologies of work with maladjusted children and young people, may be involved. Thus, during the organization of the formative stage of the experiment, the specialists of the Charitable Foundation "Kharkiv Charitable Foundation "Blago" and the Charity Fund of Charitable Organization "Caritas-Ukraine" in order to create opportunities for increasing the professional competence of future specialists of the social sphere to prevent the maladjustment of pupils, provided conditions for their preventive social and pedagogical activities with the "risk" group of adolescents and children who moved from the Anti-Terrorist Operation (ATO) area to the city of Kharkiv, subjects of probation, children from needy families and families with a lot of children, on a voluntary basis. Also, future social pedagogues and social workers within the framework of social interaction with the educational schools of the partner network (School No 36, Gymnasium No 43, School No 134, School No 156, Gymnasium No 169 of the city of Kharkiv) organized and conducted a number of events: with class leaders and the pedagogical team ("Using origami techniques in social and pedagogical activities for the prevention of aggressive behavior of pupils", "Using ethnopedagogical means in preventing deviant behavior of pupils", "Prevention of bullying in children and youth environment", etc.); with pupils ("What do I know about trafficking in human beings?", "I choose to be healthy", "Parallel virtual world: the possibility of self-assertion or the illusion of opportunities", "We are different, but we are equal!", etc.), and also developed informational booklets for parents in order to improve their pedagogical culture on the problem of prevention of maladjustment of pupils ("Prevention of alcohol addiction in adolescents", "Prevention of bullying in the study environment", "Prevention of aggressive behavior of younger pupils through means of fairy tales", "Prevention of sexual deviations in pupil behavior", "Prevention of deviant behavior of younger schoolchildren from "at risk" families, by using literary means", etc.).

An important direction in shaping the professional skills of future specialists in the social sphere is the organization of joint seminars, tournaments and conferences with specialists of other higher educational institutions. For this purpose, we have since 2008 on the basis of H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University organized an annual inter-university students' scientific and practical conference "Actual problems of research in the field of social pedagogy and social work", as well as in conjunction with the Department of Social Pedagogy of the Kharkiv Humanitarian and Pedagogical Academy, on their base, starting in 2013, the launch of scientific and practical workshop for social professionals, in which future social pedagogues and social workers from different universities have the opportunity to get acquainted with the results of research of leading scientists in social sphere and present results of their

research and publish a thesis. During the above-mentioned events, students also have the opportunity to expand their own professional contacts with leading scholars and specialists in the social sphere, which, as experts, take on workshops and conferences.

Discussions

The analysis of the research results on the problem of the professional training of future specialists in the social sphere allowed us to confirm the need to create the necessary conditions for the creation, in the process of their professional training and professional competence development, of the motivational (Bogdanova, 2016; Grishchenko, 2011; Melnyk, 2017), cognitive (Gurenko, 2013; Karpenko, 2007), practical (Vainola, 2009; Polishchuk, 2011) and personal (Olefir, 2016; Kaidalova, 2008; Melnyk and Pypenko, 2017) aspects of professional readiness for a certain kind of professional activity. Taking into account the aforesaid, we have organized a pedagogical experiment to verify the effectiveness of the impact on the formation of the professional competence of future social pedagogues and social workers to prevent the maladjustment of pupils, of the developed system of their professional training to the specified type of activity in the conditions of the created professionally directed environment on the basis of institution of higher education and bases of practice of the partner network of social institutions that carry out relevant activities with a designated contingent.

The representativeness, validity and reliability of the results obtained during the experimental study are provided by using a set of methods that are tailored to suit its purpose, tasks and reproduction possibilities.

Conclusions

According to the results of the introduction of the formative stage of the experimental study, it can be argued that the students of the experimental group with the introduction of the developed system of professional training, which provided for the gradual implementation of the five stages (introduction, professional training, professional adaptation, professionalization and professional mastery), there is a steady dynamics growth of indicators with all major research criteria. Among the qualitative changes one can distinguish the following characteristics: growth of social activity, confidence in own professional ability and independence in the performance of professional tasks; manifestation of the facilitation position in interaction with pupils who are prone to maladjustment; development of professional mobility and readiness to solve problems of prevention of maladjustment of children and youth in various social institutions, which testifies to the growth of their professional competence in preventing maladjustment of pupils.

Further research needs to be done to determine the dynamics of quantitative changes in the level of professional training of future specialists in the social sphere based on the above-mentioned criteria and indicators based on the results of the control phase of the pilot study.

References

- Bezpalco, O. (2015). Kompetentnisnyi spektr maibutnoho sotsialnoho pedahoha yak osnova profesionalizmu [Competence spectrum of the future social pedagogue as the basis of professionalism]. *Problemy osvity – Problems of Education*, 84, 60–64. [in Ukrainian]
- Bohdanova, I. M. (2016). Protses pidhotovky maibutnikh fakhivtsiv sotsionomichnoi sfery [The process of training future specialists of the socionomic sphere]. *Naukovyi visnyk Pivdenoukrainskoho natsionalnoho pedahohichnoho universytetu im. K. D. Ushynskoho – Scientific Journal of K. D. Ushinsky Southern Ukrainian National Pedagogical University*, 1(108), 13–18. [in Ukrainian]
- Honcharenko, S. U. (2010). *Pedahohichni doslidzhennia. Metodolohichni porady molodym naukovtsiam* [Pedagogical research. Methodological advice for young scientists]. Vinnytsia: Planer. [in Ukrainian]
- Hrynova, V. M. (2014). Pro spivvidnoshennia poniat “profesionalizm”, “profesiina kultura”, “profesiina kompetentnist”, “profesiina pidhotovka” [On the correlation of the concepts of “professionalism”, “professional culture”, “professional competence”, “professional training”]. *Pedahohika ta psykholohiia – Pedagogy and Psychology*, 45, 1–11. [in Ukrainian]
- Hryshchenko, S. V. (2011). *Samovdoskonalennia maibutnikh fakhivtsiv sotsialnoi sfery* [Self-improvement of future specialists in the social sphere]. Chernihiv: ChNPU. [in Ukrainian]
- Hurenko, O. (2013). *Profesiina pidhotovka sotsialnoho pedahoha: teoretyko-praktychnyi kontekst* [Professional training of social teacher: theoretical and practical context]. Donetsk: LANDON-XXI. [in Ukrainian]
- Iadov, V. (2007). *Strategiia sotsiologicheskogo issledovaniia. Opisanie, obieiasnenie, ponimanie sotsialnoi realnosti* [The strategy of sociological research. Description, explanation, understanding of social reality]. Moscow: Omega-L. [in Russian]
- Kaydalova, L. G. (2008). Formuvannia profesiinoi kompetentnosti maibutnikh fakhivtsiv [Formation of professional competence of future specialists]. *Pedahohika, psykholohiia ta medyko-biolohichni problemy fizychnoho vykhovannia i sportu – Pedagogy, Psychology and Medical-Biological Problems of Physical Education and Sports*, 1, 60–63. [in Ukrainian]
- Kapska, A. Y. (2010). Deiaki aspekty profesiinoi pidhotovky sotsialnykh pedahohiv i sotsialnykh pratsivnykiv [Some aspects of the professional training of social educators and social workers]. *Visnyk Hlukhivskoho natsionalnoho pedahohichnoho universytetu im. O. Dovzhenka – Bulletin of O. Dovzhenko Glukhiv National Pedagogical University*, 15, 12–16. [in Ukrainian]

- Karpenko, O. H. (2007). *Profesiina pidhotovka sotsialnykh pratsivnykiv v umovakh universytetskoi osvity: naukovo-metodychnyi ta orhanizatsiino-tehnolohichni aspekty* [Professional training of social workers in the conditions of university education: scientific-methodical and organizational-technological aspects]. Drohobych: Kolo. [in Ukrainian]
- Kharchenko, S. Ya. (2006). *Sotsializatsiia ditei ta molodi u protsesi sotsialno-pedahohichnoi diialnosti: teoriia i praktyka* [Socialization of children and youth in the process of socio-pedagogical activity: theory and practice]. Lugansk: Alma mater. [in Ukrainian]
- Kostina, V. (2017). Model of professional competence of future social pedagogues and social workers to prevent maladjustment of pupils. In A. Bereza (Ed.), *Development and modernization of pedagogical and psychological sciences: experience of Poland and prospects of Ukraine* (pp. 1–19). Lublin: “Baltija Publishing”.
- Kostina, V. (2018). System of training of future social pedagogues and social workers to prevent maladjustment of students. In M. Kiedrowska (Ed.), *European vector of contemporary psychology, pedagogy and social sciences: the experience of Ukraine and the Republic of Poland* (pp. 160–181). Sandomierz: “Baltija Publishing”.
- Kraevskii, V. V. (2001). *Metodologija pedagogiki* [Methodology of Pedagogy]. Cheboksary. [in Russian]
- Kyverialg, A. A. (1980). *Metody issledovaniia v professionalnoi pedagogike* [Research methods in professional pedagogy]. Tallin: Valgus. [in Russian]
- Melnyk, Yu. (2017). Study of trends of students’ demand for the formation of competences by higher educational institutions. *Science and Education*, 5, 128–134. doi:10.24195/2414-4665-2017-5-22
- Melnyk, Yu., & Pypenko, I. (2017). Innovative potential of modern specialist: the essence and content. In Yu. B. Melnyk (Ed.), *Psychological and pedagogical problems of modern specialist formation* (pp. 9–16). Warsaw: ANAGRAM. doi:10.26697/9789669726094.2017.9
- Mishchuk, L. I. (1997). *Teoretyko-metodychni osnovy profesiinoi pidhotovky sotsialnoho pedahoha u zakladakh vyshchoi osvity* [Theoretical and methodological foundations of vocational training of social teacher in higher education institutions]. (Doctoral dissertation, Zaporizhzhia State University, Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine). Retrieved from <http://www.lib.ua-ru.net/diss/cont/34563.html> [in Ukrainian]
- Olefir, V. O. (2016). *Psykhologhiia samorehuliatcii subiekta diialnosti* [Psychology of self-regulation of the subject of activity]. (Doctoral dissertation, Kharkiv Engineering and Pedagogical Academy, Kharkiv, Ukraine). Retrieved from <http://www.pdpu.edu.ua/doc/vr/olefir/dis.pdf> [in Ukrainian]
- Polishchuk, V. (2011). Stanovlennia profesionalizmu sotsialnoho pedahoha na osnovi komponentiv indyvidualnoho stylu yoho diialnosti [Becoming a professional social teacher based on the components of the individual style of his activity]. *Molod i rynek – Youth and the Market*, 4, 38–43. [in Ukrainian]
- Teslenko, V. V. (2007). *Teoriia i praktyka sotsialno-pedahohichnoi pidtrymky ditei z obmezenymy mozhlyvostiamy v promyslovomu rehioni* [Theory and practice of social and pedagogical support of children with disabilities in the industrial region] (2nd ed.). Lugansk: Alma mater. [in Ukrainian]
- Vainola, R. Kh. (2009). *Pedahohichni zasady osobystisnoho rozvytku maibutnoho sotsialnoho pedahoha v protsesi profesiinoi pidhotovky* [Pedagogical bases of personal development of the future social pedagogue in the process of professional training]. (Doctoral dissertation, M. P. Drahomanov National Pedagogical University, Kyiv, Ukraine). Retrieved from <http://www.enpuir.npu.edu.ua/bitstream/123456789/125/3/Vainola.pdf> [in Ukrainian]
- Zvierieva, I. D. (Ed.). (2013). *Entsyklopediia dlia fakhivtsiv sotsialnoi sfery* [Encyclopedia for professionals in the social sphere]. Kyiv, Symferopol: Universum. [in Ukrainian]

Cite this article as:

Kostina, V. V. (2018). Verification of the system of preparation of future specialists of the social sphere for the prevention of maladjustment of pupils in various social institutions. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 1(1-2), 12–20. doi:10.26697/ijsa.2018.1-2.02

The electronic version of this article is the complete one and can be found online at: <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/en/archive>

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>).

SOCIAL SCIENCES. Education & Educational Research

ORIGINAL RESEARCH**Behavioral Tendencies of Single Parent Students****Author's Contribution:**

- A** – Study design;
B – Data collection;
C – Statistical analysis;
D – Data interpretation;
E – Manuscript preparation;
F – Literature search;
G – Funds collection

Usakli H.¹ ABCDEFG¹ Sinop University, Turkey**Received:** 20.09.2018; **Accepted:** 12.10.2018; **Published:** 30.11.2018**Background and Aim of Study:****Abstract**

A Family is social unit of two or more people related by blood, marriage, or adoption and having a shared commitment to the mutual relationship. The definition of single parent is someone who has a child or children but no husband, wife, or partner who lives with them. Death of a partner and divorce are main causes of being single parent. Children are affected by divorce in many different ways, varying by the circumstances and age of the child. Children whose ages are seven to twelve are much better at expressing emotions and accepting parentage breakage, but often distrust their parents, rely on outside help and support for encouragement, and may manifest social and academic problems.

The aim of the study: to find out teachers opinion of single parents' students' behavioral tendency.

Material and Methods:

This qualitative study represents 30 teachers' opinions on single parent students' problems.

Results:

Not only in deep theoretical framework but also recent studies underline the importance of healthy family relation on child wellbeing. Every child may have potential for single parent in nowadays society. Experienced elementary teachers claim that single parent students are more submissive and aggressive. In addition of this, they are less assertive when comparing to their two parents counterparts.

Conclusions:

Not only school psychologists and guidance practitioners but also teachers and school principles should be aware of the potential single parent students' needs. Being more assertive or aggressive creates fewer opportunity for single parent students. Productive society will be raised with only equal sublimation of all children's developments.

Keywords:

single parent students, elementary teachers, behavioral tendencies; assertiveness; aggressiveness; submissiveness.

Copyright:

© 2018 Usakli H. Published by Archives of International Journal of Science Annals

DOI and UDC

DOI 10.26697/ijsa.2018.1-2.03; UDC 37.014.68::316.62-055.52-058.832

Conflict of interests:

The author declares that there is no conflict of interests

Peer review:

Double-blind review

Source of support:

Departmental sources

Information about the author:

Usakli Hakan (Corresponding Author) – <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4307-2226>; husakli@yahoo.com; Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor, Department of Elementary and Early Childhood Education; Sinop University; Sinop; Turkey.

Introduction

Behaviour can be defined as the way in which an individual behaves or acts. It is the way of an individual's conducting herself/himself. Behaviour should be viewed in reference to a phenomenon, an object or person. It can be seen in reference to society norms, or the way in which one treats others or handles objects. Therefore, behavior is the way of an individual's acting towards people, society or objects. It can be either bad or good. It can be normal or abnormal according to society norms. Society will always try to correct bad behaviour and try to bring abnormal behaviour back to normal (UNESCO, 2000, p. 9).

The behavior can be defined as the movement of the organization that can be viewed or measured in any way. Learning is relatively permanent change in an organism's behavioral repertoire as a result of experience.

The family, which consists of parents and children, is very important for human life. Starting from loving and loving the child who comes from within a family in the world develops a healthy personality in accordance with the needs of his/her physical, mental and mental needs and obtains the most comprehensive information about the society to live in. The child, who has completed the socialization and education process with the help and contributions of the parents of the parents, gains a successful social life. A child observes a family communication based on mutual love, respect, sharing and solidarity, has a better relationship with the people around him (Şentürk, 2012, p. 124).

Pre-school children learn about social behaviour in the family, where rules of behaviour are specified according to the family structure. These rules determine the social behaviour of the child. Families apply various kinds of control when educating their children about social behaviour. Parents sometimes explain why the child must abide by a rule and other times they just demand that she/he does it. The relation between the self control of the adult and her control over the child may be of interest.

Deficiency of mother or father can cause lack of behavioral performance for any children. What is the reason of any children's having single parent?

Nowadays, divorce is a very ordinary event. In each state in the United States, every two new marriages result in a divorce (Schaie and Willis, 1996). Also in Europe, the rate of divorce has increased in the last two decades (Jonsson, Njardik, Olafsdottir, and Gretarsson, 2000, p. 101).

The family is defined as a complex social structure consisting of a common past, shared association, emotional attachment, individual members of the family, and individuals who plan action to meet the needs of the entire family (Nazli, 2003). The family is one of the effective institutions that guide children on social development, adaptation and socialization (Yavuzer, 2001). Feldman and Wentzel (1990) argue that families can provide their children with social acceptance thanks to the child-centered education they will give their children. The core of family that constitutes the smallest unit of social structure can

sometimes be seen as an institution where parents and children are together. Due to different reasons, the family cannot fulfill its function fully, and as a result, it can lead to a bad situation. Familial changes; due to death, divorce, temporary and persistent divisions are called fragmented or single-parent families (Soyaslan, 1998). Broken family cannot fulfill its expected responsibilities due to its fragmented structure and some reasons.

Children who grow up in fragmented or single-parent families fail to fulfill their socialization tasks (Uluğtekin, 1991). The violent conflict created by the incompetence in the family causes the divorce by weakening the relationship between the parents, and as a result of these divorces, a number of anti-social behaviors such as high anxiety, aggressiveness and shyness are observed in children (Ulug and Candan, 2008). A child who cannot see as much support and love in a single parent will go on to show this need constantly (Yörükoğlu, 2004).

A child belonging to a broken family has constant internal conflict. At the end of these conflicts, they accused the family of children and showed an attitude towards them (Wolf, 1998). Without the ability to solve the problem, the child will face deeper problems in the future because he cannot solve his anti-social behavior (Morganett, 2005). The research revealed that divorce has negative consequences on children such as depression, stress, loneliness, irritability, and lack of attention (Herwig, Wirtz, and Bengel 2004; Jackson, 2000).

The effects of divorce on children:

Wade and Tavis (1990) investigate this issue from the attachment frame.

Thirty years ago, divorce was rare and shameful. Today, divorce is as common as the flu and often strikes as unpredictably, to couples married only a year as well as to couples married for decades, affecting 1 million children a year. A child born today has a 40 percent chance of living through a second parental divorce by age 18. At least, the stigma of being different is no longer a matter; we know a child who complains that she has "only" one set of parents (Wade and Tavis, 1990, p. 485).

Despite its increasing prevalence, divorce continues to be troubling, difficulty, and painful for children of all ages – just as it is troubling for most divorcing couples. One reason is that human beings do not break their attachments lightly, even bad attachments (Berman, 1988; Bowlby, 1988). Married couples who fought constantly are often surprised to discover, once separated, how emotionally attached they remain to each other. Children often persist in their attachment to cold or abusive parent long after the parents have abandoned them.

According to longitudinal studies, the effects of divorce depend on the child's gender, age, at the time of the parents' divorce, and whether you are looking at immediate or long-term reactions (Wallerstein, 1984; Wallerstein and Blakeslee, 1989):

Preschool-age children (ages 2 to 6) are the age group which most immediately distressed by their parent's

divorce, yet this group does best in the long run. Preschoolers become extremely needy and anxious. Being egocentric in their thinking, they blame themselves for the divorce (“Daddy is leaving because I left my toys on the stairs”). A year and a half later, about half of these children, especially the boys, are still deeply troubled. After five years, more than a third of them are still moderately to severely depressed. However, most have forgotten the distress and fears they felt at the time of the divorce and are less burdened by the divorce than older children until adolescence. Yet most of them still speak sadly of the disruption and some of them still have fantasies of their parents’ reconciliation. Almost all of them remain emotionally attached to their fathers, whether the father visits them often or rarely, predictably or erratically.

Elementary – school age children (ages 7 to 12) are not as likely to blame themselves for the divorce, but most feel abandoned and lonely nevertheless. They are better than preschoolers at expressing their feelings, but they have trouble in managing conflicting emotions toward the custodial parent, such as anger and sadness. They often fear that if they make that parent angry, he or she will leave them too.

Adolescents (ages 13 to 18) report frequent feelings of anger, sadness, shame, helplessness, and a sense of betrayal by the parents. They tend to cope with distancing themselves from their parents, remaining aloof even a year or more later. Girls may respond to parental divorce by becoming sexually precocious (Hetherington, M. Cox, and R. Cox, 1985). Boys may become sexually insecure and threatened, acting out their feelings through drug use and aggression. Other boys become “supermacho,” exaggerating the male role. Because of their greater cognitive maturity, adolescents are better able than younger children to see the divorce as mainly the parents’ problem. But for the same reason, they often become more distrustful of the institution of marriage itself.

College – age students (ages 18 to 22) intellectually understand and accept the reasons for their parents’ divorce, but this understanding does not reduce their emotional upheaval. Many of them report depression, stress, and feeling of insecurity. They are old enough to feel empathy for their parents, yet they often worry that no one appreciates their own grief and confusion (Cooney, Smyer, Hagestad, and Klock, 1986).

Overall, girls adjust to divorce more easily than boys, and one reason seems to be that boys suffer more by being separated from the father when the mother has custody (Beech-Lublin, 1985; Guidubaldi and Perry, 1985). Children who live in joint custody or in custody of the same-sex parent show significantly more competence, maturity, cooperativeness, and self-esteem than children living with the opposite-sex parent (Meyer and Simons, 1998).

A child’s ability to cope with divorce also depends on whether the parents settle into amicable (or at least silent) relations or continue to feel angry and conflicted. Children will eventually recover from the parents’ divorce, unless the parents continue to quarrel about visitation rights, take each other to court, or fight

with each other at every visit (Ash and Guyer, 1988; Wallerstein and Blakeslee, 1989). From the standpoint of children’s adjustment, an amicable divorce is better than a bitter marriage, but a prolonged and bitter divorce is worst of all (Wade and Tavris, 1990, p. 485-486). Divorce not only negatively affects children but also unwanted side affect for woman (Kader, 2018).

Not only divorce but also incertion is another issue for single parenting. Hairston (2007) highlights this issue. Prisoners are not lone individuals operating without social ties or consequences. They are members of families, and have family roles, commitments and obligations. Incarceration involves not only the physical separation of prisoners from society, but separation from their families, children and friendship networks as well. Research shows that prisoners and their families identify numerous financial, social and emotional issues associated with parental incarceration. Incarceration of a parent is very much a family matter. It has long-range economic, emotional and social consequences that affect prisoners, families and that can affect children’s well-being.

Every year, millions of parents separate, divorce, or remarry. Many writer have focused on the negative reactions (e.g., depression, anxiety, conduct problems) that children sometimes exhibit in response to these changes, but marital transitions are stressful for both parents and children (King, 1992). Therapists and others often focus on the divorce itself without considering the experience that predict and follow the event. Clinicians who have this restricted view tend to conceptualize a child’s psychology.

During this period (infantile – genital period ages 3-4 or so) the child experiences strong ambivalent feelings, seeking the parent of the opposite sex as a lover, but at the same time both fearing and loving the parent of the same sex. An adequate resolution of the Oedipus situation occurs when the child rejects the sexual and at the same time, identifies with the parent of the same sex. By identifying with the same-sex parent, the child both assuages feelings of fear of reprisal and incorporates the traits of the same-sex parent, the traits that made that parent win the love of the other. In effect, the boy identifies with his father and seeks to adopt his father’s characteristics. This means that the boy identifies with his father and seeks to adopt his father’s traits, the traits of masculinity. In like fashion, the girl identifies with the mother and tries to behave in those feminine ways that apparently have made her mother successfully attractive. The girl does the same with her mother. This is the way Freudian theory accounts for the development of masculine and feminine characteristics that fit the mode of the society into which the child is raised (Thomas, 1983, p. 242).

If the quality of affectional relationships at this time (basic trust versus basic mistrust ages between 0 and 1) is poor, with the mother emotionally rejecting the baby while tending to its physical needs, the sense of trust is damaged. This sets a poor foundation for the trust-mistrust ratio on which the child is to build the rest of his life (Thomas, 1983, p. 270).

Children's Behavioral Tendencies.

The work on assertiveness is the book "Your Perfect Right. A Guide To Assertive Living" written by Alberti and Emmons which is used as a source in many research. In this book, the authors state that a behavior can be in three different forms: assertive, aggressive, and non-assertive (submissive). The aggressive behavior in these forms of behavior is described as follows:

"The form of assertive behavior makes it possible for us to defend ourselves, to express our feelings fairly and comfortably, and to use our rights without violating others' rights" (Alberti and Emmons, 1998, p. 6) and to free from equality and unnecessary worries in human relations.

Aggressive behavior leads to the feeling of being trivial and hurt by anyone who is against this behavior (the buyer itself). As the other person does not recognize his/her rights, the receiver feels himself broken, humiliated and defensive (Alberti and Emmons, 1998, p. 44).

In aggression, the goal is to go our own way to win whatever it is. So aggression is usually destructive both physically and psychologically. Aggressive people are not interested in the interests, rights, desires and needs of others. With regard to aggression, the following points should be considered:

- Aggression usually leads to aggression (violence raises violence).
- Aggressive people are one who are undesirable, unwilling and unpopular.
- People do not want to have relation with aggressive people. They are hesitant to help them when they need it.
- Aggression allows a person in aggressive behavior to feel good for a very short period of time, but over time the person feels bad (Sorensen, 2005).

People who are often in abstinent behaviors are those who deny themselves, are arrested, broken, worried, allow others to make choices on their behalf, and cannot reach the target they desire (Alberti and Emmons, 1998, p. 45).

Submissive people cannot tell their true thoughts, contribute to the formation of an idea, and feel themselves worthless. Thus, the general conclusions of shy behavior can be summarized as follows:

- Not able to really meet what you want or what you need.
- Less respect from others.
- Short-term stress reduction (Sorensen, 2005).

The basic goal in assertiveness is to find the best solution for all people. Assertiveness takes into account that everyone has equal rights and responsibilities. That is why the form of aggressive behavior is based on win-win solution. Possible key outcomes of an assertive behavior may be like this:

- It is possible to meet the needs of a person exhibiting a form of assertive behavior.
- The pattern of assertive behavior allows us to be controlled.
- The form of assertive behavior helps to increase our confidence in ourselves.

- It is observed that people who exhibit a form of assertive behavior have decreased stress (Back, 1982). Greenberg (2002) points out the main points of these three behaviors. In assertive behavior, a person expresses himself comfortably and meets his needs. He does not hurt others while doing these things and he feels good. In the form of non-initiative behavior, the person denies their wishes to satisfy others. It sacrifices its own needs to meet the needs of others. In aggressive behavior, one tries to exert himself by acting as he wishes others to spend (Greenberg, 2002, p. 95).

Assertiveness is not just about earning at all costs but on the contrary, creating needs and rights fairly (Rogers, 2002, p. 55). When we want to be assertive, we have to look at the eyes of the person, but we must not shake our finger very closely to show it. We must use a clear, calm, serious tone of voice clearly (Rogers, 2002, p. 134).

Emmer, Evertson, and Worsham (2003) state that there are three skill requirements for effective communication within communication skills in teaching. These skills are constructive assertiveness, empathic response and problem solving. Constructive assertiveness involves explicitly expressing the subject matter involved, insisting on correcting misconduct, resisting against compulsion and subjugation. In this case, it is apparent that there are three elements of constructive agility. These include the ability to express the problem or situation clearly, to have a pronounced body language (eye contact but not threatening to the opposite side, not the stiffness of the spine and the matching of the face expression), and resistance to appropriate behavior or problem solving (Emmer et al., 2003, p. 147-148).

The aim of the study. To find out teachers opinion of single parents' students' behavioral tendency. The significance of this study is that there are few number of studies conducting on single parent children' problems in terms of parent specialist such as psychologist or social worker view. Studies on teachers' opinion on single parents' students' behavior is too rare.

Material and methods

Working Groups. This study was designed as qualitative research. 30 elementary school teachers who had ten or more years experienced in teaching joined in the study. The working group was familiar with basic problems of single parent children such as economic and academic. The group was highly skilled with teaching.

Data Collection. 30 participant elementary school teachers joined a conference on "Children Action Tendency" submitted by the author of this study. The conference duration was held 90 minutes. After the conference teachers answered three open ended questions:

1. What do you think about single parents' children over all?
2. What is your opinion on single parents' children behavioral tendencies such as assertiveness, aggressiveness and submissiveness?

3. Do you think that you are capable of coping with single parents' children behavioral problems?

There were three questions asked to participants as open-ended. These individual interviews were recorded. The approximate duration of interviews is 10 minutes. 300 minutes interviews records were transcribed as 32 pages of written data (Times New Roman 12, spacing 1.5).

This study was designed by qualitative research methods using document review technique. These kind of studies aim to depict the past or present as it exists (Karasar, 2008, p. 77). Qualitative research is frequently used in anthropology, philosophy, humanistic psychology, sociology, social psychology, environmental psychology, linguistics. However, qualitative research is also used in interdisciplinary studies such as educational sciences. Qualitative research offers a flexible working environment for researchers. In qualitative research, interview methods have positive contributions such as giving flexibility to researchers, dominating responses, following nonverbal behaviors, providing control over the environment and getting in-depth information (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2008).

Data analysis and reliability. The two terms are sine qua non for all researches not only quantitative but also qualitative ones. Reliability is a term which is used in quantitative research to indicate the consistency of measurement. The term is also applied to some qualitative research, particularly that which adopts a realist epistemology. In qualitative research, the evaluative criteria that are applied are more commonly transparency and trustworthiness. Validity is the extent to which research measures or reflects what it claims to. It is most meaningfully used in research with a realist epistemology (Frost, 2011, p. 108).

The thematic model can be applied to a wide range of narrative text, including narratives produced in interviews and written documents. The analyst can start the thematic analysis by the open coding of data. The steps in the categorical content analysis described by Lieblich, Tuval-Mashiach, and Zilber (1998) can be used in the process of thematic analysis. The categorical content analysis focuses on thematic similarities and differences between narratives generated in interviews. The analytical approach of

Lieblich et al. (1998, p. 112-113) involves breaking the text into smaller units of content.

Results

This study reflects only a small partial of very wide range of scientific research project. The research title is "Preparing a Psycho-Educational Program for Identifying Problems of Single Parents and Solving These Problems". To make visible study for problems of single parents' students, this qualitative study was designed. In this study, 30 elementary teachers who are experienced more than ten years were interviewed. Before these interviews, those teachers were participated a conference on behavioral tendency. In this conference, the author of this study explained to the teachers what is assertive, aggressive and submissive behavior of any person especially elementary student. 90 minutes conference on Children Action Tendency were held for experienced elementary teachers.

After the conference, the working group (30 teachers) were interviewed with three open ended questions.

Themes from their answers are shown as Table 1 as in below.

In question one "What do you think about single parents' children over all?" asked to the teachers. 26 teachers out of 30 gave positive statements. According to the teachers there are a few students of single parents in all classes and it is pity that they are problematic. In statistically this seems to be in high ratio (86%).

"What is your opinion on single parents' children behavioral tendencies such as assertiveness, aggressiveness and submissiveness?" asked to the teachers as a second question. According to the teachers single parents' students are failure in presenting assertive behavior. Girls seem to be submissive whereas boys are more aggressive when comparing to their same age and sex counter parts of two parents' students. 28 teachers out of 30 agree with this situation and this is also in high percentage (93%).

The last question was "Do you think are you capable of cope with single parents' children behavioral problems?" 20 teachers out of 30 (66%) stated that they have lack of information how to cope with single parents' students. Even if they know something to intervene there will be time problem to devoting to problematic students.

Table 1. Teachers response on behavioral tendencies of single parents' students.

Questions	Response	f (frequency)	% (percentage)	Sample from responses
1. What do you think about single parents' children over all?	Socially, emotionally, behavioral problems	26	86	I think there are several such kind of students an all class but sometimes it is difficult to guess who they are. I believe and I know that most of them have social, emotional and behavioral problems.
2. What is your opinion on single parents' children behavioral tendencies such as assertiveness, aggressiveness and submissiveness?	More submissive or aggressive and less assertive	28	93	Especially single parent girls are more submissive. I know a girl she was with her two parents and was very lively. But now even she prefers being far away from her old friends. Ohh boys are every time problematic yelling fighting whatever you think as undesired behavior.
3. Do you think are you capable of cope with single parents' children behavioral problems?	Professionally no and limited time	20	66	I know something but where and when I should intervene.

Discussion and Conclusions

In this qualitative study, 30 experienced elementary classroom teachers reflected their ideas on behavioral tendencies of single parents' students. In three open ended questions, teachers are agreed with there are problems of single parents' students.

Submissiveness seems to be main characteristics of single parents girls. Whereas boys of single parents display more aggressive behavior when they compare their two parents counterpart. Submissive or aggressive behavior is an example of unwanted behavior at home or at school in children (Alberti and Emmons, 1998, p. 45). How should these behaviors be avoided and how can these children present desired behavior? First of all, the behavior of the children should be well known. Unfortunately, parents and teachers make mistakes while interpreting children's behaviors. It must be realized that not only at home, but also in school, desired behaviors of children. Parents and other members of the household have the opportunity to closely monitor the child's behavior. In the school environment, tests and non-test techniques are used to identify individuals in the context of school guidance services. Apart from testing techniques such as skills tests, success tests and interest inventories, it is used to identify students with non-test techniques based on observation, self-expression and others' perspectives. However, it appears that there is limited scope for student recognition techniques within the programs of primary and secondary school guidance services. The techniques of individual recognition conducted in school guidance services are to uncover the differences between the students and to give them an opportunity to help them to develop more effectively. However, besides all these intensive help services, parents are worried about some of their children's behavior (Emmer et al., 2003)

Especially Sociometry Test which is the measurement tool of sociometry and popularity of children is very useful. Some apparatus such as The Loneliness Scale, Self-Respect Scale measurement tools with the tests are insufficient in the definition of the students. These inadequacies can result from the inability to observe student behaviors carefully. Group psychological counseling and guidance processes are effective in the close observation of the students.

Psycho-education groups are created for people to acquire certain skills, to understand certain topics, and to help them during difficult transition periods of life.

Both the process and the performance in this process and the output to the product can lead to changes in the ability of the students to recognize them both by their parents and their teachers (Uşaklı, 2007). It is very important that children be directed to their appropriate fields of art and sport in order for them to come from the top of unwanted behaviors after their parents or specialists are recognized. Drama in the classroom, circle clock, psycho-education activities will also help children develop constructive attitudes.

Single parent's children are sensitive groups. As parents, school principals and teachers, we should be aware of their developmental needs. About 2000 years

ago, the great wise Hillel said: "If I am not for myself, who will be for me? And if I'm just for myself, what am I? And if not now – when?" Some of the most important lessons that we can teach our children include how they will express themselves and their balance of interest when they consider the rights and feelings of others, and when should parents teach these lessons? As Hillel asked, "If not now – when?" (Deluty and Uşaklı, 2009).

Acknowledgments

This work was supported in the Sinop University for Scientific Research Project; project number EĞTF-1901-18-05. I would like to thank Sinop University Scientific Research Project Office workers.

References

- Alberti, R., & Emmons, M. (1998). *Atılğanlık Hakınızı Kullanın* [Your Perfect Right: Assertiveness and Equality in Your Life and Relationships] (7th ed.). Ankara: HYB Yayıncılık. [in Turkish]
- Ash, P., & Guyer, M. (1986). The functions of psychiatric evaluations in contested child custody and visitation cases. *Journal of the American Academy of Child Psychiatry*, 25(4), 554–561.
- Beech-Lublin, V. (1985). *Factors that facilitate child adjustment following divorce*. Los Angeles: American Psychological Association.
- Berman, W. (1988). The role of attachment in the post-divorce experience. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 54, 496–503.
- Bowlby, J. (1988). *A secure base: Parent-child attachment and healthy human development*. New York: Basic Books.
- Cooney, T., Smyer, M., Hagestad, G., & Klock, R. (1986). Parental divorce in young adulthood: Some preliminary findings. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 53, 470–477.
- Deluty, R., & Usakli, H. (2009). Saldırgan, atılğan ve cekingen davranma (ma) yolları [The ways (not) to behave aggressively, impulsively, and timidly]. *Coluk Cocuk – Child and Family*, 86, 20-21. [in Turkish]
- Emmer, E. T., Evertson, C. M., & Worsham, M. E. (2003). *Classroom management for secondary teachers* (6th ed). Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- Feldman, S. S., & Wentzel, K. R. (1990). Relations among family interaction patterns, classroom self-restraint, and academic achievement in preadolescent boys. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 82, 813–819.
- Frost, N. (2011). Discourse Analysis Approaches. In N. Frost (Ed.), *Qualitative Research Methods in Psychology Combining Core Approaches*. New York: Open University Press.
- Greenberg, J. S. (2002). *Comprehensive Stress Management* (7th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill Companies.
- Guidubaldi, J., & Perly, J. D. (1985). Divorce and mental health sequelae for children : A two year

- follow-up of a nationwide sample. *Journal of the American Academy of Child Psychiatry*, 24(5), 531–537.
- Hairston, C. F. (2007). *Focus on Children with Incarcerated Parents: An Overview of the Research Literature*. Baltimore: The Annie E. Casey Foundation.
- Herwig, J. E., Wirtz, M., & Bengel, J. (2004). Depression, partnership, social support, and parenting: Interaction of maternal factors with behavioral problems of the child. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 80, 199–208.
- Hetherington, E. M., Cox, M., & Cox, R. (1985). Long-term effects of divorce and remarriage on the adjustment of children. *Journal of the American Academy of Child Psychiatry*, 24(5), 518–530.
- Jackson, A. P. (2000). Maternal self-efficacy and children's influence on stress and parenting among single black mothers in poverty. *Journal of Family Issues*, 21, 3–16.
- Jonsson, F. H., Njardik, U., Olafsdottir, G., & Gretarsson, S. J. (2000). Parental divorce: Long-term effects on mental health, family relations and adult sexual behavior. *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology*, 41, 101–105.
- Kader, M. U. (2018). *Stepping into a new struggle: low-ses divorced single mothers' experiences in relation to family resources and social policies in Turkey*. (Unpublished master's thesis). Middle East Technical University: Ankara.
- Karasar, N. (2008). *Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemi: Kavramlar, İlkeler, Teknikleri* [Scientific research method: concepts, principles, techniques]. Ankara: Nobel. [in Turkish]
- Lieblich, A., Tuval-Mashiach, R., & Zilber, T. (1998). *Narrative research: reading, analysis and interpretation*. London: Sage Publications.
- Meyer, K. G., & Simons, V. A. (1988). Questions and issues related to social policies as they impact on very young children and their families who are caught in the divorce process. San Francisco: American Orthopsychiatric Association.
- Morganett, S. R. (2005). *Yaşam becerileri ergenler için grupla psikolojik danışma uygulamaları* [Life skills group psychological counseling practices for adolescents]. Ankara: Pegem Akademi Yayıncılık. [in Turkish]
- Nazlı, S. (2003). *Aile Danışmanlığı* [Family Counseling] (2nd ed.). Ankara: Nobel. [in Turkish]
- Schaie, K. W., & Willis, S. L. (1996). *Adult development and ageing* (4th ed.). New York: Harper Collins.
- Şentürk, Ü. (2012). Parçalanmış Aile Çocuklarının Eğitimdeki Başarı/Başarısızlık Durumu (Malatya Örneği 2006) [Educational Success/Failure Status of Fragmented Family Children (Malatya Case 2006)]. *Sosyal Politika Çalışmaları Dergisi – Journal of Social Policy Studies*, 12(7), 105–126. [in Turkish]
- Sorensen, S. (2005). *Assertiveness and understanding it by Stuart Sorensen – RMN*. Retrieved from <http://www.mhsanctuary.com/articles/assert.htm>
- Soyaslan, D. (1998). *Kriminoloji (suç ve ceza bilimleri)* [Criminology (crime and criminal science)]. Ankara: Ankara Üniversitesi. [in Turkish]
- Uşaklı, H. (2007). Aile ve Öğretmenlerin Öğrencileri Tanıma Becerilerindeki Değişmeler [Changes in Family and Teachers' Students' Recognition Skills]. *Sempozyum: XVI. Ulusal Eğitim Bilimleri Kongresi*. Retrieved from https://www.pegem.net/Akademi/kongrebildiri_detay.aspx?id=5132 [in Turkish]
- Uluğ, M., & Candan, G. (2008, March). Parçalanmış (Boşanmış) Aile Sorununun Öğrenciye Etkisi [The Student Effect of the Broken (Divorced) Family Problem]. *Eğitim Psikolojisi Sempozyumu – Educational Psychology Symposium*, İstanbul. [in Turkish]
- Uluğtekin, S. (1991). *Hükümlü çocuk ve yeniden toplumsallaşma* [Convicted child and re-socialization]. Ankara. [in Turkish]
- UNESCO. (2000). Behaviour Modification – MODULE 4. In W. Guez, & J. Allen (Eds.). France: UNESCO.
- Wade, C., & Tavis, C. (1990). *Psychology* (2nd ed.). New York: Harper-Collins.
- Wallerstein, J. S. (1984). Children of divorce: Preliminary report of a ten-year follow-up of young children. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 54(3), 444–458.
- Wallerstein, J. S., & Blakeslee, S. (1989). *Second chances: Men, women, and children a decade after divorce*. New York: Ticknow and Fields.
- Yavuzer, H. (2001). *Çocuk Psikolojisi* [Child Psychology] (20th ed.). İstanbul: Remzi Kitabevi. [in Turkish]
- Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (2008). *Sosyal Bilimlerde Nitel Araştırma Yöntemleri* [Qualitative research methods in the social sciences] (6th ed.). Ankara: Seçkin Yayıncılık. [in Turkish]

Cite this article as:

Usakli, H. (2018). Behavioral tendencies of single parent students. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 1(1-2), 21–27. doi:10.26697/ijsa.2018.1-2.03

The electronic version of this article is the complete one and can be found online at: <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/en/archive>

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>).

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Empathy in the Structure of Psychological Competence of the Teacher of the Higher Educational Institution

Author's Contribution:

Mitina S. V.^{1 ABCDEFG}

- A** – Study design;
- B** – Data collection;
- C** – Statistical analysis;
- D** – Data interpretation;
- E** – Manuscript preparation;
- F** – Literature search;
- G** – Funds collection

¹ *V. I. Vernadsky Taurida National University, Ukraine*

Received: 08.10.2018; **Accepted:** 01.11.2018; **Published:** 30.11.2018

Abstract

Background and Aim of Study:

The efficiency of pedagogical activity depends not only of the level of professional knowledge and abilities of the teacher but also of the presence for him of the personality qualities necessary for optimal cooperation. One of such professionally-meaningful qualities of the teacher is the empathy able to do the process of education emotionally comfortable and productive.

The aim of the study: to explore of level of empathy's display of the teachers depending on experience of their pedagogical activity.

Material and Methods:

Theoretical (analysis and synthesis of the psychological literature); empirical (pilot study). 97 teachers of the higher educational institutions participated in the study; at the age of 27 to 62 years, with the work experience from 1 year to 30 years.

Results:

The results obtained indicate that the empathy is the important component in the structure of the professional competence of the teacher of the higher educational institution, and also that the empathic ability of the teacher is transformed with the development of life and professional experience. The empirical research shows the lowest rates of empathy among the teachers with the work experience of more than 25 years and among the young teachers with the work experience up to 10 years.

Conclusions:

It is concluded that there is the dependence of the empathy of professional experience, necessary to develop the empathy both at the stage of the training of the future teachers in the higher educational institutions and in the process of continuous professional education.

Keywords:

competence, psychological competence, teacher, pedagogical activity, empathy.

Copyright:

© 2018 Mitina S. V. Published by Archives of International Journal of Science Annals

DOI and UDC

DOI 10.26697/ijsa.2018.1-2.04; UDC 159.942:378.124.08

Conflict of interests:

The author declares that there is no conflict of interests

Peer review:

Double-blind review

Source of support:

Departmental sources

Information about the author:

Mitina Svitlana Vladimirovna (Corresponding Author) – <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-9520-0272>; mitina.svetlana68@gmail.com; Doctor of Philosophy in Psychology, Associate Professor, Professor of the Department of Psychology and Pedagogy; V. I. Vernadsky Taurida National University, Kyiv, Ukraine.

Introduction

The analysis of the psychological and pedagogical literature on this issue suggests that the most of the scientists (Holovan, 2014; Strelnikov, 2013; Kyrychok, Mitina, and Ilchenko, 2017; Melnyk, 2017) determine the professional competence of the teacher as the complex integrated personal education, which includes the theoretical knowledge, the practical skills, the experience and personal qualities, which generally allows effectively to carry out the educational activities and provides the process of development and self-development of personality.

Strelnikov (2013) notes that in the professional competence of the teacher of the higher educational institution is primarily the psychological and didactic procedures for interacting with the students, motivational-value, cognitive, affective and conative components, as well as the system of professionally important qualities and abilities of the teacher. The studies of Melnyk (2017) show that the most popular competences are of the instrumental and systemic ones, in particular: cognitive, methodological, technological and linguistic abilities.

As is generally known, the essence of pedagogical activity is the interpersonal interaction with the students. For this purpose, the teacher needs the knowledge and communicative skills to establish the business contact, the emotional attitude for future cooperation. Vitvytska (2012, p.69) notes the techniques that ensure the effectiveness of the interaction: - the ability to show interest and respect to the student, to understand his position during communication; - to own the means of non-verbal communication; - the tolerant attitude to all participants of the educational process.

As we see, the psychological competence of the teacher is inextricably linked with his communicative competence. The results of our previous studies have shown that it is the communicative competence of the teacher that is one of the important components of his psychological skills. The communication in the activities of the teacher is not only the means of pedagogical communication, but also the condition for the improvement of the professionalism, the source of personal development, and is also the means of influence on the students (Mitina, 2016).

In the structure of the communicative competence of the teacher Shestopaliuk (2011) distinguishes the following professionally important personal qualities, namely: - the interest to the people and the work with them; - the presence of need and ability to communicate; - the verbal and non-verbal abilities; - the ability to show empathy to the people. We share this point of view and believe that the successful professional activity of the teacher is impossible with the absence or low level of empathy.

Recently, the problem of empathy has been actively studied by the scientists in the professional context as the important property of the personality of socioeconomic professions (Kuntsevskaya, 2004; Popova and Horvat-Yanushevskaya, 2013) and as the factor of the effectiveness of the pedagogical process (Goroshit and

Hen, 2016).

According to the scientist Ilin (2013, p. 39), the empathy is the source of altruism and the factor of the helping behavior, so the more the person is prone to the empathy, the higher his willingness to giving help in the particular case. The author underlines that for the manifestation of the empathy, is obligatory the emotional response – the empathy, namely a person's awareness that his feelings are the reflection of his partner's feelings.

The empathic personality differs from the other people by his ability to see the others positively; the quick orientation in the situations of interaction; the democratic and altruistic strategies of interaction prevail; the openness and sensitivity to social emotions and moral feelings (Dolby, 2013). The characteristics of the empathic personality is the stability, the tolerance towards the disadvantages of others, which in our opinion is necessary for the effective professional activity of the teacher.

Sannikova (2014) considers the empathy as the property of the personality in which structure the three levels are distinguished: 1) the formal-dynamic, including the dynamic and qualitative (modal) properties of the empathy, reflecting the psychological essence of the empathic process; 2) the content-personal, concerning the choice of space for experiencing the empathy, the moral and ethical content of its object; 3) the imperative level reflecting the public and individual ideas about the existing socio-cultural "norms" of empathic manifestations.

According to Baron-Cohen and Wheelwright (2004), empathy is about spontaneously and naturally tuning into the other person's thoughts and feelings, whatever these might be there are two major elements of empathy. The first is its cognitive component (understanding the others feelings and the ability to take their perspective), the second one is the affective component (an observer's appropriate emotional response to another person's emotional state).

Orishchenko (2015) also defines the empathy as the stable integral property of the person. The author underlines that the leading psychological characteristic of the person with a high level of the empathy is the social activity, the interpersonal skills, the sincere interest to the person, the orientation on the understanding of another, the sensitivity and the responsiveness. It is precisely the kindness, the tolerance, the sufferance towards others makes such people capable to the sympathy and the empathy.

The aim of the study: to explore of level of empathy's display of the teachers depending on experience of their pedagogical activity.

Material and methods

The following research methods were applied: theoretical (analysis and synthesis of the psychological literature); empirical (pilot study, questionnaires). The study was conducted at the basis of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology of the Institute of Postgraduate Education of the Bogomolets National Medical University, Kyiv. The sample composed the

teachers of the higher educational institutions, a total number of 97 persons aged from 27 to 62 years, with the pedagogical work experience from the 1 to 30 years. The following psychodiagnostic techniques were applied: questionnaire “Diagnostics of the level of empathic abilities” (Boyko, 1996), multifunctional ϕ -criterion of Fisher.

Results

The results of diagnostics of the level of empathy of the teachers show that the most feck of the teachers (73%) have the low (16%) and below average (57%) level of manifestation of empathy, which may indicate to certain emotional “callousness” of the teachers. Only to 27% of the studied group the empathic abilities are at the sufficient level, which manifests itself in the ability to understand and “feel” the psycho-emotional state of the students.

The analysis of the integral characteristics of the empathy (see Table 1) showed that more than half of the teachers have the low or understated level of attitudes toward the manifestation of empathy. Perhaps that it is precisely the lack of focus on establishment of the personal contacts, the conviction that it is inappropriate to show interest for the experiences and

problems of the students, limits the range of emotional responsiveness and reduces the ability to empathy’s manifestation.

The “penetrating ability in the empathy” as the important communicative property of the person, allowing to create the atmosphere of openness and trust that in turn contributes to the empathy’s manifestation. And vice versa, the atmosphere of tension and suspicion, the absence prevents the functioning of the rational channel of the empathy, which is why the majority of the studied group of the teachers have low and below average values for this indicator of the empathy.

The necessary condition for empathic personality is the ability to identify, namely the ability to put oneself to the place of another person and understand him on the basis of empathy. However, as the results showed, more than half of the teachers have the low and below-average level of identification, which in turn blocks the intuitive channel of the empathy and obstructs for empathy’s manifestation on the whole.

At the next stage of the study, we analyzed the dependence of the manifestation of the level of the empathy of the experience of the teacher’s professional activities. The results are presented in Figure 1.

Table 1. The characteristics of integral indicators of the empathy.

The characteristics of the empathy	The frequency of manifestation (%)			
	high	average	below the average	low
The rational channel of the empathy	3	28	30	39
The emotional channel of the empathy	11	43	19	27
The intuitive channel of the empathy	11	34	22	33
Adjustment to the empathy	3	34	27	36
The penetrating ability in the empathy	4	33	31	32
The identification	5	38	23	34

Figure 1. The manifestation of the level of the empathy of the teachers depending of work experience.

As can we see in the Figure 1, the lowest rates of the empathy are observed to the teachers with the work experience of more than 25 years and to the young teachers with the work experience up to 10 years.

Table 2 presents the results of the statistical analysis of the differences in the frequency of manifestations of the low level of integral characteristics of the empathy, depending on the experience of the professional activity of the teachers.

To prove the statistical significance of the differences in the frequency of manifestations of the low level of the empathy in the studied groups of the teachers, we applied the multifunctional φ -criterion of Fisher. If $\varphi_{exp.}$ is less than $\varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$, so the differences of indicators in the studied samples are not statistically significant, and if $\varphi_{exp.}^{**}$ is more than $\varphi_{0.01} = 2.28$, so it can be argued that the differences of indicators in the studied samples are significant. If $\varphi_{0.05} < \varphi_{exp.}^* < \varphi_{0.01}$, so the differences in the manifestation of low level of the empathy among the studied groups of the teachers can be considered significant at the 5% level of significance.

Thus the differences in the functioning of the intuitive channel of empathy of teachers with the work experience of 10 to 25 years and the teachers who work in the university up to 10 years or for more than 25 years are statistically significant. Also the differences in the manifestation of the ability to the empathy and to the identification are statistically significant.

Discussion

In the process of research, we held the point of view of Boyko (1996, p. 74) on the empathy, as the means of reflecting the inner world of another person, allowing to understand the causes and the consequences of his behavior. Understanding the empathy as

comprehension the psycho-emotional state of another person implies the existence of three empathic channels: rational, emotional and intuitive. The rational empathy characterizes the focus of attention, intellection on the condition and behavior of another person. The emotional empathy is the ability to enter into the energy field of another, to understand his inner world. The intuitive empathy is the subconscious processing of information about another person, which is based on the past experience and determines the personality's ability to foresee its behavior.

In our opinion, the low level of the empathy of the teachers with the little experience is due to insufficiently developed communication skills and empathic abilities. The beginners teaching specialists cannot yet build the effective pedagogical interaction, find it difficult to the search of the individual approach to each student, they do not always succeed in creating the atmosphere of trust working with the academic group. It should be noted that the empathic ability of the individual is transformed with the development of life and professional experience.

Stojiljkovic, Djigić, and Zlatković (2012) notes that the empathy is essential for successful carrying out the various professional roles of teachers. The pedagogical empathy as the teacher's personality's quality has the particular social and practical importance for optimizing and regulating the interpersonal relations with the students and improving the efficiency and the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. The pedagogical empathy is the powerful tool, in realizing the functions of cognition of the students by the teacher, its presence ensures to the teacher the success in the professional activities.

Table 2. The results of the mathematical-statistical analysis of the differences of manifestations of the empathy of the teachers.

The characteristics of the empathy	work experience up to 10 years (n=24) / work experience from 10 to 25 years (n=31)	work experience up to 10 years (n=24) / work experience over 25 years (n=42)	work experience from 10 to 25 years (n=31) / work experience over 25 years (n=42)
The rational channel of the empathy	$\varphi_{exp.} = 0.46$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$	$\varphi_{exp.} = 0.93$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$	$\varphi_{exp.} = 0.48$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$
The emotional channel of the empathy	$\varphi_{exp.} = 0.26$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$	$\varphi_{exp.} = 0.54$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$	$\varphi_{exp.} = 0.41$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$
The intuitive channel of the empathy	$1.64 = \varphi_{0.05}$ $\leq \varphi_{exp.}^* = 1.77$ $\leq \varphi_{0.01} = 2.28$	$\varphi_{exp.}^{**} = 2.47$ $\geq \varphi_{0.01} = 2.28$	$\varphi_{exp.} = 0.59$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$
Installation to the empathy	$\varphi_{exp.} = 0.67$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$	$\varphi_{exp.} = 0.39$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$	$\varphi_{exp.} = 1.22$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$
The penetrating ability in the empathy	$\varphi_{exp.}^{**} = 2.53$ $\geq \varphi_{0.01} = 2.28$	$\varphi_{exp.} = 1.37$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$	$\varphi_{exp.} = 1.52$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$
The identification	$\varphi_{exp.} = 0.35$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$	$\varphi_{exp.} = 1.33$ $\leq \varphi_{0.05} = 1.64$	$1.64 = \varphi_{0.05}$ $\leq \varphi_{exp.}^* = 1.89$ $\leq \varphi_{0.01} = 2.28$

The studies of Goroshit and Hen (2016) suggest that empathic teachers were found to possess a higher level of morality and excellent communication with students which in turn encourages empathic peer relationships and the successful motivation of their students and also contributes to the improvement of the academic performance of the students.

The studies of Zhuravlova (2007, p. 71) show that as the empathic process functions become more complex, the level of emotional tension of the subject of interaction changes in the direct proportion to this, which makes it possible to speak about the decrease or increase of the level of emotional inclusion of the subject to interpersonal interaction. Thus, in the process of professional development of the teacher, it takes place the development and the transformation of the empathic.

The results of our study show that the optimal level of empathy's manifestation is typical for the specialists with the teaching experience of 10 to 25 years. These are already the highly qualified specialists who have the developed skills of the professional communication; they understand students better, thanks to the developed professional competence. However, as evidenced the results of our research, to the teachers with the work experience of more than 25 years, the decrease of level of the empathy is observed. In our opinion, the teachers with the long work experience, who have been in intensive interaction with the students for a long time, some of whom are unmotivated to learn, trigger the psychological defense mechanism in the form of the emotional disregard and indifference. In so far as empathic person is more emotionally vulnerable, the decrease of the empathy in this case can be viewed as the acquired stereotype of the teacher's professional behavior, which allows to him to use metered the psycho-emotional resources and protect himself from excessive emotional stress. On the other hand, as shown by the results of our previous studies, the emotional callousness, the indifference to the feelings of the students and colleagues, can be the symptom of the teacher's emotional burnout (Mitina, 2017).

The studies of Cooper (2004) show that despite a desire to support and relate deeply to pupils, teachers were continually constrained by the conditions in which they worked, namely: the fragmented and rigid curriculum; the bureaucracy of modern education and the large numbers of pupils and low frequency of contact. The author notes that in consequence of these teachers are show lack of care towards individuals.

Conclusions

Summarizing the results of the study, it can be stated that the empathy is the important component in the structure of the professional competence of the teacher of the higher educational institution, which provides the constructive interaction of subjects of the educational process and contributes to its effectiveness. The pedagogical empathy involves the teacher's emotional attitude towards the student, the understanding of his emotional experiences, and giving

help to the student in overcoming the life difficulties and negative psycho-emotional states. In so far as the level of empathy's manifestation depends of the practice and experience of necessary to form it both at the training stage of the future teachers in the higher educational institutions and in the system of continuous professional education.

Acknowledgments

Thanks to all the teachers who participated in this study. The study was supported by the leadership of the Bogomolets National Medical University, Kyiv.

Source of support

Departmental sources of the Institute of Postgraduate Education of the Bogomolets National Medical University, Kyiv.

References

- Baron-Cohen, S., & Wheelwright, S. (2004). The empathy quotient: an investigation of adults with Asperger Syndrome or high functioning autism, and normal sex differences. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 34(2), 163–175. doi:10.1023/B:JADD.0000022607.19833.00
- Boyko, V. V. (1996). *Energiia emotsii v obshchenii: vzgliad na sebii i na drugikh* [The energy of emotions in communication: a look at yourself and others]. [DX Reader version]. Retrieved from: <http://osp.kgsu.ru/library/PDF/389.pdf> [in Russian]
- Cooper, B. (2004). Empathy, interaction and caring: Teachers' roles in a constrained environment. *Pastoral Care in Education*, 22(3), 12–21. doi:10.1111/j.0264-3944.2004.00299.x
- Dolby, N. (2013). The decline of empathy and the future of liberal education. *Liberal Education*, 99(2), 60–64.
- Goroshit, M., & Hen, M. (2016). Teachers' empathy: can it be predicted by self-efficacy? *Teachers and Teaching: Theory and Practice*, 22(7), 805–818. doi:10.1080/13540602.2016.1185818
- Holovan, M. S. (2014). Profesiina kompetentnist vykladacha vyshchoho navchalnoho zakladu [Professional competence of a teacher of a higher educational institution]. *Problemy suchasnoi pedahohichnoi osvity: Pedahohika i psykholohiia – Problems of modern pedagogical education: Pedagogy and Psychology*, 44, 79–88. [in Ukrainian]
- Ilin, E. P. (2013). *Psikhologiia pomoshchi. Altruizm, egoizm, empatiia* [Psychology of help. Altruism, selfishness, empathy]. St. Petersburg: Piter. [in Russian]
- Kuntsevskaya, A. V. (2004). Empatiia u systemi profesiinykh zdatnostei fakhivtsiv sotsionomichnykh profesii [Empathy in the system of professional skills of specialists in socio-occupational professions]. *Aktualni problemy psykholohii – Actual problems of psychology*, 7(2), 193–197. [in Ukrainian]

- Kyrychok, V. A., Mitina, S. V., & Ilchenko, A. A. (2017). Communicative competence formation of a higher educational institution lecture by means of interactive technology in teaching and education. *Deutscher Wissenschaftsberichter*, 1, 38–41. doi:10.19221/2017.18
- Melnyk, Yu. (2017). Study of trends of students' demand for the formation of competences by higher educational institutions. *Science and Education*, 5, 128–134. doi:10.24195/2414-4665-2017-5-22
- Mitina, S. V. (2016). Psykholohichna skladova v strukturi profesiinoi kompetentnosti vykladacha vyshchoho navchalnoho zakladu [Psychological component in the structure of professional competence of a teacher of a higher educational institution]. In T. V. Kolbina, & Yu. B. Melnyk (Eds.), *Aktualni pytannia osvity i nauky – Current issues of education and science* (pp. 301–305). Kharkiv: KRPOCH. doi:10.26697/9789669726070.2017.301 [in Ukrainian]
- Mitina, S. (2017). The factors of emotional burnout of the teacher of the higher educational institution. *Psychological and pedagogical problems of modern specialist formation*, 1, 34–37. doi:10.26697/9789669726094.2017.34
- Orishchenko, O. A. (2015). Psikhologicheskii portret lichnosti s vysokim urovnem empatii [Psychological portrait of a person with a high level of empathy]. *Science and Education a New Dimension. Pedagogy and Psychology*, 3(28), 86–88. [in Russian]
- Popova, T. S., & Horvat-Yanushevska, I. I. (2013). Empatiia ta yii rol u vzaiemodii sotsialnoho pratsivnyka z kliientom [Empathy and its role in the interaction of a social worker with a client]. *Naukovi pratsi. Sotsiologhiia – Scientific works. Sociology*, 225(213), 116–120. Retrieved from: <http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Npchsusoc> [in Ukrainian]
- Sannikova, O. P. (2014). Kontynualno-iierarkhichna model emotsiinosti [The continuum-hierarchical model of emotionality]. *Nauka i osvita – Science and Education*, 1, 44–50. [in Ukrainian]
- Shestopaliuk, O. V. (2011). Formuvannia profesiinoi kompetentnosti vykladacha VNZ [Formation of professional competence of a teacher of higher education]. *Suchasni informatsiini tekhnolohii ta innovatsiini metodyky navchannia v pidhotovtsi fakhivtsiv: metodolohiia, teoriia, dosvid, problem – Modern information technologies and innovative methods of training in the training of specialists: methodology, theory, experience, problems*, 28, 4–9. Retrieved from: <http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Sitimn> [in Ukrainian]
- Stojiljkovic, S., Djigić, G., & Zlatković, B. (2012). Empathy and teachers' roles. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 69, 960–966. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.12.021
- Strelnikov, V. Iu. (2013). Komponenty profesiinoi kompetentnosti vykladacha vyshchoi shkoly [Components of the professional competence of the teacher of higher education]. *Humanitarnyi visnyk – Humanitarian Herald*, 28(1), 278–285. Retrieved from: <http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/gvdpdu> [in Ukrainian]
- Vitvytska, S. S. (2006). *Osnovy pedahohiky vyshchoi shkoly* [Fundamentals of higher education pedagogy]. [DX Reader version]. Retrieved from: <http://194.44.152.155/elib/local/sk702798.pdf> [in Ukrainian]
- Zhuravlova, L. P. (2007). *Psykhologhiia empatii* [Psychology of empathy]. [Monograph]. Retrieved from: <http://eprints.zu.edu.ua/209381.pdf> [in Ukrainian]

Cite this article as:

Mitina, S. V. (2018). Empathy in the structure of psychological competence of the teacher of the higher educational institution. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 1(1-2), 28–33. doi:10.26697/ijsa.2018.1-2.04

The electronic version of this article is the complete one and can be found online at: <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/en/archive>

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>).

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Program of Psychological Rehabilitation of the National Guard of Ukraine Military Personnel Participated in Combat Actions

Author's Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

Prykhodko I. I.¹ ABCDEFG

¹ National Academy of National Guard of Ukraine, Ukraine

Received: 23.10.2018; **Accepted:** 15.11.2018; **Published:** 30.11.2018

Abstract

Background and Aim of Study:

Combat actions that have taken place over the past four years in eastern Ukraine have a negative impact on the physical and mental health of the combatants. Under these conditions, the psyche of military personnel operates on the brink of its own resources, and prolonged participation in hostilities can lead to the development of post-traumatic stress disorder. Therefore, timely measures of prevention and control of combat stress, psychological rehabilitation of military personnel after engagement in combat will significantly reduce psychogenic injuries, prevent the emergence of mental disorders from combatants.

The aim of the study: to develop, scientific ally substantiate and to test a program of psychological rehabilitation of combatants.

Material and Methods:

To determine the effectiveness of the program of psychological rehabilitation at the beginning and at the end was used by authorial diagnostic of mental disorders methodology "Psychological Safety of Personality", as well as "The Questionnaire Evaluating the Effectiveness of Psychological Training" after completing the psychological training. In total, 70 military men of the National Guard of Ukraine from all regions of Ukraine participated in the program of Psychological rehabilitation, and the practical implementation and testing of the program took place in 2017.

Results:

The program of psychological rehabilitation of combatants based on psychological training for restoring the psychological safety of a military man's personality has been developed and scientifically substantiated. The practical implementation of the program of the psychological rehabilitation of the combatants proved its effectiveness: the results of the dynamics of the components of psychological safety of a person increased on average by 16%.

Conclusions:

Proposed program of psychological rehabilitation of combatants helped to improve the mental condition of military personnel, to restore psychological resources of a person and to prevent the development of mental disorders.

Keywords:

prevention of mental disorders, psychological rehabilitation psychological training, military personnel, combat actions, combatants.

Copyright:

© 2018 Prykhodko I. I. Published by Archives of International Journal of Science Annals

DOI and UDC

DOI 10.26697/ijsa.2018.1-2.05; UDC 159.9.072(477)

Conflict of interests:

The author declares that there is no conflict of interests

Peer review:

Double-blind review

Source of support:

Departmental sources

Information about the author:

Prykhodko Ihor Ivanovich (Corresponding Author) – <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4484-9781>; prikhodko1966@ukr.net; Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor, Chief of the Scientific and Research Center for Service and Combat Activities of the National Guard of Ukraine, National Academy of National Guard of Ukraine; Kharkiv, Ukraine.

Introduction

Combat actions that has taken place in the east of Ukraine over the past four years has a negative impact on the physical and mental health of the combatants (Prykhodko, Kolesnichenko, Matsegora, Vorobyova, and Parkhomenko, 2014). Under these conditions, the psyche of the military personnel functions on the brink of their own capabilities, and continued participation in combat actions can cause chronic stress and the development of posttraumatic stress disorder (Pasichnik et al., 2011; Prykhodko, 2015).

The experience of accomplishing combat and service tasks in such circumstances has shown that professional and psychological preparedness of the military personnel is a necessary component of professional activity (Prykhodko, 2017). Thus, it is important that the military were able to learn techniques that allow to develop the necessary professionally important qualities to ensure a psychological safety of an individual (PSI), based on not only the physical survival of a military man in extreme conditions, but also to preserve the broader functioning of the individual, the specialist – the ability to act effectively and professionally (Prykhodko, 2014). Therefore, it is extremely important to implement practically into psychological support of the combat and service activity (CSA) the program for the formation, maintenance and preservation of psychological safety of an individual in the military. In addition, timely measures of prevention and control of combat stress, psychological rehabilitation of military personnel after engaging in hostilities will significantly reduce psychogenic injuries, prevent the emergence of mental disorders from combatants.

The conducted analysis of scientific researches and authors' experience of participation in psychological support of combat and service missions (CSM) under the combat conditions showed that psychological rehabilitation of the military refers to the systems and measures of psychological activities aimed at preserving and restoring the psychological safety of the individual, correction of positive mental states necessary to ensure a high level of combat capabilities of military personnel, exposed to psycho-traumatic stress factors, as well as the creation of favorable conditions for further successful execution of CSM.

The aim of the study: To develop, scientific ally substantiate and to test a program of psychological rehabilitation of combatants.

Material and methods

To determine the effectiveness of the psychological rehabilitation program at its beginning and after the end has been used the psychodiagnostic methodology "Diagnosis of Psychological Safety of an Individual" (the PSI Methodology) of an extreme activities expert (Prykhodko, 2014). It consists of 88 statements, which are united in 4 scales: "moral and communicative", "motivationally volitional", "value and semantic", "internal comfort". This PSI Methodology has allowed determining the individual structural components of the PSI by different scales and its integrative characteristic

– the PSI index, as well as their dynamics after the implementation of measures for the psychological rehabilitation of military service members. Upon its completion, the effectiveness of its conduct was also determined by means of the feedback form "Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Psychological Rehabilitation".

The cluster and correlation analyzes used (Student's t-criterion) have allowed to reveal the tightness and direction of interconnections between the indicators, reliable differences between them and increase the validity of the conclusions in the research of dynamics of the PSI in the military service members – participants of combat actions after the implementation of psychological rehabilitation measures.

Seventy military service members under the contract of the National Guard of Ukraine (NGU) from all regions of Ukraine with medium and lower levels of PSI took part in psychological rehabilitation program activities. During three rounds (April, May, and October) in 2017, the combatants experienced these activities in NGU Medical and Rehabilitation Center, Novi Sanzhary town.

Results

After the execution of the CSM in extreme (combat) conditions, based on the results of psychodiagnosis, all NGU military personnel – combatants were divided into four groups. The first group consisted of persons without significant deviations of mental condition, which maintained a high level of PSI, favorable family relationships, the ability of full-fledged social adaptation, labor and combat ability, able to continue to perform CSM qualitatively – these military service members did not need psychological rehabilitation measures. The second group included combatants with minor deviations in their duties and psychological state. They marked the lower (average) level of PSI by different scales, reduction of working capacity, difficulty in everyday life, but sufficient control over their own behavior was maintained with the help of mobilizing psychological and physical resources efforts. The third group consisted of military personnel who had an average and low level of PSI by separate scales, some signs of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), acute or chronic somatic pathology in the stage of aggravation. They were observed to have certain violations of social and professional rehabilitation, as well as problems in their personal lives. Such military men from the second and third groups required psychological rehabilitation at the NGU Medical and Rehabilitation Center. The fourth group – the persons with acute signs of mental disadaptation and mental disorders that needed an extraordinary consultation of a psychiatrist and, if necessary, were hospitalized to a specialized psychiatric department for examination and treatment. Consequently, because of the psychodiagnosis carried out using the PSI Methodology, a group of NGU military personnel participated in combat actions in the number of 70 people (representatives of the second and third groups) who were in need of psychological rehabilitation.

A special program was developed for conducting psychological rehabilitation at the Scientific Research Center of NGU Combat and Service Activity. The purpose of the psychological rehabilitation program of the NGU combatants is to restore mental health, a sense of PSI and effective social behavior.

The main tasks of psychological rehabilitation program of combatants are as following:

- 1) psychological correction of violations of the emotional, personal and behavioral sphere of the military;
- 2) improvement of the state of mental health, restoration of levels of PSI, quality of life of military service members in order to increase their social adaptation in the family, military team and society;
- 3) prophylaxis of the early marginal disorders of the mental register (including manifestations of suicidal behavior) in the military;
- 4) training of self-regulation measures (removal of stress, anxiety, aggressiveness, control of dependent behavior, training of means of self-motivation);
- 5) formation of constructive skills of social interaction in society;
- 6) mobilization of psychological resources of military personnel in overcoming the consequences of wounds, injuries, disability, relief of pain, psychological training of victims of surgery and in the postoperative period (as necessary);
- 7) monitoring of the psychological state of military personnel participating in the psychological rehabilitation program activities.

The main types of activities included in the psychological rehabilitation program of military personnel are as follows:

1. Psychodiagnostics (monitoring of individual psychological peculiarities of personality before and after psychological rehabilitation).
2. Psychological lecture.
3. Practical training on self-regulatory means (control of anger, self-motivation, etc.).
4. Psychological training for the restoration of PSI in military personnel participating in combat actions.
5. Individual consultations with combatants, conducted simultaneously irrespective of the measures of the main psychological rehabilitation program.

Before conducting a psychological rehabilitation program of combatants, specialists are involved in the distribution of the following main functions:

- 1) Counselling Psychologist – for conducting an introductory lecture, psychodiagnosis, individual consultations and practical classes, which are aimed at forming skills of self-management and desensitization, including every day relaxation measures, except for those conducted by the psychologists-trainers.
- 2) Training Psychologist for training PSI recovery in military participating in combat actions.
- 3) Family Psychologist – for group and individual trainings, consultations.
- 4) Sexologist (sex therapist) – for the group and individual trainings, consultations.

Structure of the combatants' psychological rehabilitation program is presented in Table 1.

The main component of the psychological rehabilitation program of combatants is the psychological training for the PSI restoration. Purpose of the training: the restoration of PSI as a harmonious combination of a sense of security and ability to develop and self-fulfillment.

The tasks of the psychological training for the restoration of PSI are as following:

- restoration of the PSI feeling, feeling of safety, ability to protect themselves;
- transfer of responsibility for their own lives into their own hands, restoration of their ability to manage their own lives;
- using the traumatic situation to rethink the values of their own lives;
- the use of trauma energy for post-traumatic growth.

The psychological training is intended for military personnel participating in combat operations, which have an average and low level of PSI, signs of ASR and PTSD, disorders of rehabilitation that do not reach the clinical level. The number of participants is about 12-15 people. Possible involvement of co-coach, in addition to the main trainer. The trainer should be a male psychologist who has experience of participating in combat actions.

The psychological rehabilitation work involves the movement following the vector from the “disturbed sense of safety” to “normalizing the sense of personal safety”. This movement takes place under two main conditions: 1) the creation of a safe atmosphere, a safe environment; 2) the use of psychological techniques.

Conducting psychological training in the conditions of a Medical Rehabilitation Center meets both these conditions. The basis of the training is the developed model of the PSI (Prykhodko, 2014). It involves working with the four components that form the sensation of PSI as a harmonious state that combines a sense of safety and a desire for self-realization:

- 1) satisfaction with the situation of development of own “Me” – this component “Internal comfort” initiates movement from the change of environment or from the actualization of mechanisms of self-regulation;
- 2) “Value and semantic” component allows determining the vital priorities to overcome the traumatic situation, it implements the principle: “Everything can be experienced, if you know for what”;
- 3) “Motivational and volitional” component involves understanding of the own goals and opportunities for their achievement and, accordingly, harmonious redistribution of energy for the realization of really important things and not dispersal of forces on the secondary things (especially in conditions of danger);
- 4) “Moral and communicative” component means that following the rules of interaction adopted in the surrounding society promotes the formation of a safe social environment, reduces the probability of conflicts, creates an atmosphere of promoting the realization of the goals of the person, self-realization.

Table 1. Structure of the combatants' psychological rehabilitation program

Day of training	Group work	Individual work
1 st day	<p>1. Lecture (1.0 hour): "The Consequences of Mental Traumatism". The goal is to form conscious participation in psychological events. Provide overview of the types of consequences of trauma, clinical picture of acute stress reaction (ASR) and PTSD, the possibility of psycho correctional intervention. To promote awareness of members of their current condition, eliminating the halo of exclusivity existing psychological problems, establishing a connection between psychogenic factors, the emergence and persistence of the PTSD symptoms. To acquaint with the schedule of work of the Counselling Psychologist. Answer the questions.</p> <p>2. Psychological diagnostics (1.5 hours) (the Methodology "Diagnostics of PSI").</p> <p>3. Relaxation, exercises to improve sleep (exercise "Safe Place") (0.5 hours).</p>	Individual consultations on general topics
2 nd day	1. PSI recovery training in the military along with symptoms of PTSD (3.0 hours) (lesson No. 1). The purpose – acquaintance, definition of the individual situation of development, the state of well-being.	Individual consultations on general topics
3 ^d day	<p>1. Group self-regulating classes – learning ways to overcome stress and injury.</p> <p>2. Mastering the Aliyev Keys (Keys) technique.</p>	Individual consultations on general topics
4 th day	<p>1. Group lessons with a family psychologist (2.0 hours). Goal – improvement of readaptation to the family after a long separation and the formation of a motivation for consulting a Family Psychologist.</p> <p>2. Development of anger control means (0.5 hours).</p> <p>3. Relaxation, exercises to improve sleep, the Keys technique exercises (0.5 hours).</p>	<p>1. Individual consultations on general topics</p> <p>2. Family Psychologist consultations</p>
5 th day	<p>1. Group lesson (lecture) of a sexologist / sex therapist (2.5 hours). The goal is to determine the ways of solving typical sexual problems of military personnel having stress and being after a long separation from spouses, the formation of the motivation for consulting a sexologist / sex therapist.</p> <p>2. Relaxation, exercises to improve sleep, the Keys technique exercises (0.5 hours).</p>	<p>1. Individual consultations on general topics</p> <p>2. Consultations of sexologist / sex therapist</p>
6 th day	<p>1. Training for the restoration of the PSI in military service members having signs of PTSD (3 hours) (lesson No. 2). The purpose is to work with the value-semantic part of the PSI.</p>	Individual consultations on general topics
7 th day	<p>1. Group classes on self-regulation (2.5 hours) – work with losses.</p> <p>2. Relaxation, Keys technique exercise (0.5 hours).</p>	Individual consultations on general topics
8 th day	<p>1. Group self-regulating lessons (2.5 hours) – work with dependencies.</p> <p>2. Relaxation, Keys technique exercise (0.5 hours).</p>	Individual consultations on general topics
9 th day	Training for the restoration of the PSI in military personnel having signs of PTSD (lesson No. 3) (3.0 hours). The purpose is to work with the motivational-volitional part of the PSI.	Individual consultations on general topics
10 th day	<p>1. Group lessons with a Family Psychologist (2.5 hours). The goal is to improve rehabilitation for the family life after a long separation and to formulate a motivation for consulting a Family Psychologist.</p> <p>2. Relaxation, exercises to improve sleep, Keys technique exercise (0.5 hours).</p>	<p>1. Individual consultations on general topics</p> <p>2. Family Psychologist consultations</p>
11 th day	<p>1. Group lesson (lecture) of a sexologist / sexologist (2.5 hours). The goal is to identify ways to solve typical sexual problems of military service members having stress and being after a long separation from their spouses, and to motivate for consulting a sexologist / sex therapist.</p> <p>2. Relaxation, exercises to improve sleep, Keys technique exercise (0.5 hours).</p>	<p>1. Individual consultations on general topics</p> <p>2. Consultations of sexologist / sex therapist</p>
12 th day	<p>1. Group sessions on self-regulation (2.5 hours) – a means for self-motivation.</p> <p>2. Relaxation, Keys technique exercise (0.5 hours).</p>	Individual consultations on general topics
13 th day	<p>1. PSI recovery training in the military having symptoms of PTSD (lesson No. 4) (3.0 hours). The purpose is to work with the moral and communicative part of the PSI.</p>	Individual consultations on general topics
14 th day	<p>1. PSI recovery training in the military having symptoms of PTSD (last lesson No. 5 – drawing of future life paths in-group) (3.0 hours).</p> <p>2. Psychological diagnostics (1.0 hour) ("PSI Diagnostics" Methodology).</p>	Individual consultations on general topics

All components are interconnected and act as a single mechanism. Of course, the outer layer of the mechanism – “moral and communicative component” – is the most heavily used; it provides safety, beginning with common everyday situations of interaction. The central component is the “inner comfort” or the satisfaction with the situation of the development of its own “Me” – is actualized when a productive and safe life under the old “scheme” becomes impossible (most people are able to endure significant “inconveniences” for a long time before making a major change in their lives).

It should be noted that the peculiarity of working with military who have expressed signs of ASR and PTSD is that the leader (coach) or the participants do not interpret the feelings, statements of military men, which imparts special requirements to the stage of “reflection” – the discussion of exercises. When organizing classes it is necessary to avoid excessive activity (very shortly used exercises for “warm-up”, open confrontation), each session and complicated relaxation exercises are over. Classes have a relatively short duration of 3 hours (and not 6-8, as in the deep immersion training (Lefterov, 2008). In exercising the imagination, you must constantly monitor the course of what the participant has to imagine (the coach continuously guides the participant’s imagination by the verbal commands); it is not need to require closing eyes for those whose exercises are aimed at working with imagination (do not insist if some participants refuse to close their eyes). The trainer briefly announces the content of the presentation exercises so that participants can feel their control over the process. The trainer tells the content and meaning of the classes at the beginning of the psychological training and each lesson in an accessible, concise form. Such awareness reduces stress and increases the effectiveness of training (Lefterov, 2008).

The use of unusual for everyday activities of the military personnel of drawing during the training, work with tales, with cards, meditation is explained to participants as a means that allows faster development of new forms of behavior, views on problem solving, which allows to bypass acquired, habitual habits.

Exercises that under psychological training aimed at self-regulation in stress should relate to situations of insignificant or moderate severity (traumatism). If a participant considers that an exercise suits him for the self-regulation of heavier classes, he may use it during individual consultations under the supervision of a counseling psychologist who fully possesses all exercises that are mastered by the participants during the training.

In addition, the training is intensified by group lessons on the development of other methods of self-regulation, conducted by a counseling psychologist, and which correspond to the sequence of training sessions. Such a division allows to keep in mind of the participants the structure of the training and to understand better the various ways of self-regulation, which reinforces the individual approach and improves the assimilation of the material.

Group classes determine the direction of development, actualize the need for change, and promote awareness of the existence of problems and the need for assistance in overcoming them.

Individual consultations, which are conducted in parallel (simultaneously) with group sessions, are intended for more profound working out of problems, work with more intimate questions, which participants of the training for one reason or another cannot make during group discussion.

Psychological training is carried out in a relatively small room, with proper form, with good lighting (participants should have the opportunity to be arranged in the circle in such a way so that their back is protected by the walls of a room). The window must be relatively small or make it possible to provide distance from it (if the training participants avoid places near the window, then the coach takes that place). Chairs should be reliable (with a high back and no wheels), there should be no deaf cubes (uncontrolled for the sight of the space), shadows, extra furniture, etc.

During the training, the leader should determine the status of the participants visually, with the help of verbal self-descriptions and Luscher techniques. To remove negative states use relaxation exercises, “H.M. Aliyev Key”, “Safe place” and “Change of seasons” (see Tables 1, 2; including instructions for the current, not traumatic situation). The trainer should use active listening and support techniques. If available, participants of the training should discuss the issue of providing support to comrades who describe their traumatic experiences (it is necessary to voice support methods that are acceptable for this group).

The psychological training for the restoration of the PSI of military service members-participants of combat operations contains five classes for three hours each. The training rules are as follows: the group should not have complete confidentiality, so it is necessary to speak only about what they are ready to share; do not criticize; do not give advice; respect others; you can be angry with the words you hear at the training, but you will take from the training exactly that you need.

Simultaneously with the training in the organization of recreation of military men were held master classes on painting fingers, folk painting, pottery (work with clay), dancing, yoga, animal therapy (horseback riding).

The results of the psychodiagnosis carried out using the PSI Methodology before and after the activities of the psychological rehabilitation program of military service members-participants in combat operations are presented in Table 3.

As we can see from the given data, the indicators of PSI dynamics after the implementation of psychological rehabilitation measures are statistically significantly higher among military servicemen than on individual scales, as well as in general, according to the PSI index, on average they have improved by 16% (see Figure 1).

In addition, to assess the feedback on the effectiveness of the combatants’ psychological rehabilitation program activities, a questionnaire was developed and questioning had been performed (see Table 4).

Table 2. Structure of the program of psychological training to restore the psychological safety of the personality of the combatants.

Module name	The purpose of the lesson, the name of the exercise	Time
Psychodiagnosics of peculiarities of PSI of combatants		
Module 1	Lesson No. 1	3 hours
Correction of negative psychic reactions and states that arise during the performance of the CSM in extreme conditions, improvement of sleep quality, increase of the value of life.	<p>The purpose is to actualize the component of the PSI “internal comfort” as a satisfaction with the development of its own “Me”. Forming of an active position to overcome the danger situation, actualization of available means of self-regulation or the development of new ones, the need for which a person feels.</p> <p>A sequential implementation of the following exercises is previewed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. “Acquaintance” – is aimed at identifying with the social group and understanding their own peculiarities. 2. “Life way” – is intended for awareness of the individual situation of development. 3. “Change of seasons” – is aimed at representing the traumatic situation in which participated the soldier, the presentation of the seasons and their successive changes (autumn, winter, spring, summer). 4. “Recommendation” – designed to find own strengths, training confidence in the situation of the public presentation, increase self-esteem. 	
Module 2	Lesson No. 2	3 hours
Development of value-semantic sphere in combatants.	<p>The purpose is to actualize the value-semantic component of the PSI.</p> <p>Awareness of the desire to achieve in their own lives, the guidelines for the sake of what it is worth living, the transfer of all the difficulties of military service, put their lives at risk. Definition, for which it is necessary to undergo psychological rehabilitation, to change the ways of behavior, which during the service became familiar, comfortable. Sequential exercise:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. “Understanding of Goals” – is intended to help understand the relationship between their own goals and daily activities, prioritizing priorities. 2. “Epitaph” – aimed at discussing and determining the life goals, values of the combatants. 3. “The meaning of life” – designed to withdraw from the subconscious goals, which soldiers seek. 	
Module 3	Lesson No. 3	3 hours
Increase of resistance to stress, formation of productive coping strategies, activation of professional motivation, acquisition of skills for setting real professional goals, their achievement, obtaining skills of self-regulation of behavior in extreme conditions.	<p>The purpose – actualization of the motivational and volitional component of the PSI. Forming of flexibility in military men's achievement of goals, redistribution of energy in favor of more important goals, training on the use of productive copings. Sequential exercise:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. “Good in bad” – designed to identify positive moments in negative events, an attempt to correct failure in terms of utility. 2. “Steps of Achievements” – aimed at identifying and correcting the purpose of life, further professional growth. 3. “Non-book problems” – is intended for studying the solution of life problems using the symbolic field. 	
Module 4	Lesson No. 4	3 hours
Improvement of the process of adaptation to the extreme conditions associated with performing of the CSM, the development of moral and communicative, volitional qualities.	<p>The purpose – actualization of the moral and communicative component of the PSI.</p> <p>Forming of conditions for self-realization through understanding the rules for organizing interaction in a social group reduces the conflict of behavior. As a result, people have the opportunity to spend mental energy on their own goals rather than overcoming conflicts. Sequential exercise:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. “Internal justification” – manifests the character of the creative representation of the combatant, stimulates the development of creativity and imagination, the ability to emotional (impulsive) perception, improvisation, observation, development of a sense of humor. 2. “Qualities that irritates in other people” – helps each participant of the training to understand why these or other qualities can annoy him. 3. “Plasticine” – improves communication, interaction with people, joint activities, reduces aggressiveness, and identifies leaders. 4. “Rules of Civil Life” – based on the 8 basic specific rules of survival and skills required in the battle, but which complicate the civil life of Pucelik (Pucelik and Mabee, 2017): security; trust and definition of the enemy; devotion of the goal; decision-making; tactics of response; predictability and control; control of emotions; difficulty talking about the war. 	
Final lesson	Lesson No. 5	3 hours
Summarizing the training.	<p>The purpose is to update plans for the future of life.</p> <p>Forming of ideas for the future is a positive attitude towards your life, your loved ones, as well as your professional activities. Sequential exercise:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Exercise “Map of the Future” – designed to determine the ways of personal development and aspirations in professional activities. 2. Exercise “Sharing drawing of the future” improves the correction of personal goals in life and activities, modeling human behavior in society. 	
Psychodiagnosics of the PSI dynamics of combatants		1 hour

Table 3. Indicators of PSI of combatants before and after the activities of the psychological rehabilitation program (in standard units).

Scales of the method “Diagnostics of psychological safety of an individual”	Study groups (n=70)		Significance of discrepancies	
	Before implementation	After implementation	t	p
Morally communicative	94.00 ± 14.39	99.62 ± 16.11	0.94	–
Motivational and volitional	106.85 ± 10.95	114.85 ± 14.53	1.71	0.10
Value and semantic	104.54 ± 13.05	113.77 ± 15.81	1.74	0.10
Internal comfort	103.15 ± 14.69	114.23 ± 13.71	2.14	0.05
PSI index	408.00 ± 41.70	440.46 ± 57.57	1.77	0.10

Figure 1. Dynamics of indicators of psychological safety of an individual of combatants because of the program of psychological rehabilitation.

Table 4. Profile “Evaluating the effectiveness of the psychological rehabilitation program”.

No.	Question	Scale of evaluation
1	How important for you were the program topics?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
2	Did you know something new to yourself?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
3	Will you be able to apply the acquired knowledge in practice?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
4	Measure how much the program is provided with new information.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
5	How consistent and logical was the material presented?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
6	Evaluate the volume of the material outlined.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
7	How comfortably did you feel yourself during the presentation of the material?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
8	How difficult was it for you to perceive the material?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
9	Evaluate the pace of material presentation.	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
10	How much are you satisfied with trainers?	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Note. Instruction: “Dear participants of the psychological rehabilitation program! We ask you to answer the questionnaire. Your opinion about the events is very important for us. Your evaluations will help us to make our joint work more effective. All your thoughts will be taken into account when drawing up the program for its further use”.

Figure 2. Satisfaction (subjective assessment) by carrying out measures for the psychological rehabilitation of combatants.

The results of the anonymous survey showed that 83% of participants in psychological rehabilitation were satisfied with the program, 17% of respondents expressed their wish for further correction (Figure 2).

Discussion

The problem of psychologic rehabilitation of the military service members participating in combat actions always was relevant in any country of the

world, where local military conflicts had taken place (Smith, Ryan, Wingard, Slymen, Sallis, and Kritz-Silverstein, 2008; Rona, Jones, Iversen, and Hull, 2009; Wittchen et al., 2012). It acquired special importance after the “Vietnam War”, in which US troops participated, as well as other military conflicts on the territory of Afghanistan and Iraq (Browne et al., 2007; Milliken, Auchterlonie, and Hoge, 2007; Rona, Jones, Sundin, Goodwin, Hull, Wessely, and, Fear, 2012; Sundin et al., 2014). According to American and British scientists, after the fighting ended, tens of thousands of veterans committed suicide; various forms of PTSD often began to appear in other combatants, many of which broke up families, various manifestations of addictive behavior appeared (alcoholism, drug addiction, etc.) (Rona, Jones, French, Hooper, and Wessely, 2004; Schnurr, Lunney, and Sengupta, 2004; Sareen, Cox, Afifi, Stein, Belik, Meadows, and Asmundson, 2007; Hunt, Wessely, Jones, Rona, and Greenberg, 2014). As the results of the conducted research showed, such effects began to arise in connection with the failure to conduct or poor-quality conduct of measures for psychological recovery and rehabilitation (Sundin, Fear, Iversen, Rona, and Wessely, 2010; Schulte-Herbruggen and Heinz, 2012). In connection with this, veterans of combat operations and active military personnel began to develop hidden and deployed mental disorders, in particular PTSD (Andrews, Brewin, Philpott, and Stewart, 2007; Brailey, Vasterling, Proctor, Constans, and Friedman, 2007; Brewin, Andrews, Hejdenberg, and Stewart, 2012; Marx et al., 2012). Following the development of appropriate psychological rehabilitation programs, foreign scientists point out that after their practical implementation, the percentage of people who experience significant personal psychological problems and mental disorders is significantly reduced (Solomon and Mikulincer, 2006; Sundin, Fear, Hull, Jones, Dandeker, and Hotopf, 2010).

Thus, timely development and implementation of the program of psychological rehabilitation of military personnel – participants in combat operations, veterans will be able to prevent the development of severe mental disorders (PTSD, depression) or significantly reduce their number, as well as improve the process of reapplication of combatants to a peaceful life.

Conclusions

The proposed program of psychological rehabilitation of military servicemen-combatants allows to restore emotional self-regulation of an individual and to improve the neutralization of aggressive manifestations, to create higher tolerance to others, to reduce the risk of maladaptation during extreme conditions, to increase neuro-psychological stability, to improve communicative qualities and control of consciousness over behavior.

As a result of the activities of the psychological rehabilitation program, not only personal and professional qualities of the military servicemen develop, but a well-differentiated professional image of the world is being developed; in the future it is possible to predict the events of one's own life; to avoid

unwanted situations for self-realization; to develop the socio-psychological environment according to their own plan and to play a leading role in relations with others.

After conducting a psychological training for restoration of the psychological security of an individual, military service members become more open to new experiences, new ways of interaction, they are not afraid of new tasks, difficult life situations. The constructed relationship with the surrounding environment will not only allow the use of external resources in extreme situations, but will also contribute to the continuous enrichment of the soldier's personality.

References

- Andrews, B., Brewin, C. R., Philpott, R., & Stewart, L. (2007). Delayed-onset posttraumatic stress disorder: A systematic review of the evidence. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 164(9), 1319–1326. doi:10.1176/appi.ajp.2007.06091491
- Brailey, K., Vasterling, J. J., Proctor, S. P., Constans, J. I., & Friedman, M. J. (2007). PTSD symptoms, life events, and unit cohesion in US soldiers: Baseline findings from the neurocognition deployment health study. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*, 20, 495–503.
- Brewin, C. R., Andrews, B., Hejdenberg, J., & Stewart, L. (2012). Objective predictors of delayed-onset post-traumatic stress disorder occurring after military discharge. *Psychological Medicine*, 42(10), 2119–2126. doi:10.1017/S0033291712000189
- Browne, T., Hull, L., Horn, O., Jones, M., Murphy, D., Fear, N. T., ... Hotopf, M. (2007). Explanations for the increase in mental health problems in UK reserve forces who have served in Iraq. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 190, 484–489. doi:10.1192/bjp.bp.106.030544
- Hunt, E. J. F., Wessely, S., Jones, N., Rona, R. J., & Greenberg, N. (2014). The mental health of the UK Armed Forces: where facts meet fiction. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*, 5(1), 23617. doi:10.3402/ejpt.v5.23617
- Lefterov, V. O. (2008). *Psykholohichni treninhovi tekhnologii v orhanakh vnutrishnikh sprav* [Psychological training technologies in internal affairs bodies]. Donetsk: DUI. [in Ukrainian]
- Marx, B. P., Jackson, J. C., Schnurr, P. P., Nelson, M. M., Sayer, N. A., Keane, T. M., ... Speroff, T. (2012). The reality of malingered PTSD among veterans: Reply to McNally and Frueh. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*, 25(4), 457–460. doi:10.1002/jts.21714
- Milliken, C. S., Auchterlonie, J. L., & Hoge, C. W. (2007). Longitudinal assessment of mental health problems among active and reserve component soldiers returning from the Iraq War. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 298, 2141–2148.
- Pasichnik, V. I., Lipatov, I. I., Shestopalova, L. F., Prykhodko, I. I., Moldavchuk V. S., Irkhin, Yu. B. ... Stadnik, A. V. (2011). *Teoriia*

- ta praktyka psykholohichnoi dopomohy [Theory and practice of psychological help]. Kharkiv: Academy of VV MVS of Ukraine. [in Ukrainian]
- Prykhodko, I. I. (2014). *Psykholohichna bezpeka personalu ekstremalnykh vydiv diialnosti (na prykladi viiskovosluzhbovtziv vnutrishnikh viisk MVS Ukrainy)* [Psychological safety of the personnel of extreme activities (for example servicemen of Internal Troops of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine)]. Kharkiv: NUCZU. [in Ukrainian]
- Prykhodko, I. I. (2015). Psykholohichni osoblyvosti sluzhbovo-boiovoi diialnosti viiskovosluzhbovtziv Natsionalnoi hvardii Ukrainy pry provedenni antyterrorystychnoi operatsii [Psychological peculiarities of service and combat activity of military service members of the National Guard of Ukraine during the antiterrorist operation]. *Visnyk Kyivskoho natsionalnoho universytetu imeni T. Shevchenka. Viiskovo-spetsialni nauky – Bulletin of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Military-Special Science*, 2(33), 35–39. [in Ukrainian]
- Prykhodko, I. I. (Ed.). (2017). *Psykholohiia ekstremalnoi diialnosti* [Psychology of extreme activities]. Kharkiv: NA NGU. [in Ukrainian]
- Prykhodko, I. I., Kolesnichenko, O. S., Matsegora, Y. V., Vorobyova, I. V., & Parkhomenko, O. O. (2014). Psykholohichniy suprovod sluzhbovo-boiovoi diialnosti viiskovosluzhbovtziv Natsionalnoi hvardii Ukrainy v ekstremalnykh umovakh [Psychological support of military service of servicemen of the National Guard of Ukraine in extreme conditions]. *Chest i zakon – Honor and law*, 3, 68–74. [in Ukrainian]
- Pucelik, F. R., & Mcbee, A. J. (2017). *Reality wars dissociated state therapy*. Odesa: Neformat.
- Rona, R. J., Jones, M., French, C., Hooper, R., & Wessely, S. (2004). Screening for physical and psychological illness in the British Armed Forces: I: The acceptability of the programme. *Journal of Medical Screening*, 11, 148–153.
- Rona, R. J., Jones, M., Iversen, A., & Hull, L. (2009). The impact of posttraumatic stress disorder on impairment in the UK military at the time of the Iraq War. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 43(6), 649–655.
- Rona, R. J., Jones, M., Sundin, J., Goodwin, L., Hull, L., Wessely, S., & Fear, N. T. (2012). Predicting persistent posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in UK military personnel who served in Iraq: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 46(9), 1191–1198.
- Sareen, J., Cox, B. J., Afifi, T. O., Stein, M. B., Belik, S.-L., Meadows, G., & Asmundson, G. J. (2007). Combat and peacekeeping operations in relation to prevalence of mental disorders and perceived need for mental health care: Findings from a large representative sample of military personnel. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 64(7), 843–852. doi:10.1001/archpsyc.64.7.843
- Schnurr, P. P., Lunney, C. A., & Sengupta, A. (2004). Risk factors for the development versus maintenance of posttraumatic stress disorder. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*, 17(2), 85–95.
- Schulte-Herbruggen, O., & Heinz, A. (2012). Psychological trauma in soldiers – A challenge for the German armed forces. *Deutsches Arzteblatt International*, 109(35–36), 557–558.
- Smith, T. C., Ryan, M. A., Wingard, D. L., Slymen, D. J., Sallis, J. F., & Kritzer-Silverstein, D. (2008). New onset and persistent symptoms of posttraumatic stress disorder self reported after deployment and combat exposures: Prospective population based US military cohort study. *British Medical Journal*, 336, 366–371.
- Solomon, Z., & Mikulincer, M. (2006). Trajectories of PTSD: A 20-year longitudinal study. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 163, 659–666.
- Sundin, J., Fear, N. T., Hull, L., Jones, N., Dandeker, C., & Hotopf, M. (2010). Rewarding and unrewarding aspects of deployment to Iraq and its association with psychological health in UK military personnel. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 83, 653–663.
- Sundin, J., Fear, N. T., Iversen, A., Rona, R. J., & Wessely, S. (2010). PTSD after deployment to Iraq: Conflicting rates, conflicting claims. *Psychological Medicine*, 40, 367–382.
- Sundin, J., Herell, R. K., Hoge, C. W., Fear, N. T., Adler, A. B., Greenberg, N., ... Bliese, P. D. (2014). Mental health outcomes in US and UK military personnel returning from Iraq. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 204(3), 200–207. doi:10.1192/bjp.bp.113.129569
- Wittchen, H.-U., Schonfeld, S., Kirschbaum, C., Thurau, C., Trautmann S., Steudte, S., ... Zimmermann, P. (2012). Traumatic experiences and posttraumatic stress disorder in soldiers following deployment abroad: How big is the hidden problem? *Deutsches Arzteblatt International*, 109(35–36), 559–568. doi:10.3238/arztebl.2012.0559

Cite this article as:

Prykhodko, I. I. (2018). Program of psychological rehabilitation of the National Guard of Ukraine military personnel participated in combat actions. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 1(1-2), 34–42. doi:10.26697/ijsa.2018.1-2.05

The electronic version of this article is the complete one and can be found online at: <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/en/archive>

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>).

GUIDELINES FOR THE AUTHORS OF INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENCE ANNALS

For more detailed information see <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/index.php/en/instructions-for-authors/instructions-for-authors>.

Manuscript sections:

- UDC
- Manuscript title.
- All Authors' Surnames first and middle initials.
- Specify the contribution of each Author to prepare the Manuscript: ABCDEFG.
- Specify the affiliation of each Author (Name of the organization/university, country).
- Abstract.

All Manuscripts must have a structured abstract with 200-250 words in the language of Manuscript, without abbreviations. Required headings are: Background and Aim of Study, Material and Methods, Results, Conclusions.

Keywords: 5-7 words, without abbreviations.

- Introduction.
- The aim of the study.
- Material and methods (it may consist of three subsections: Participants, Organization of the Research, Statistical analysis).
- Results.
- Discussion.
- Conclusions.
- Acknowledgments.
- Source of support.
- References (more than 20) should be making up according to APA Style.
- Information about the Author/Authors.

Supplemental materials:

1. Author Agreement Form.
2. Conflict of Interest Declaration.

EDITORIAL POLICY (For more detailed information see <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/index.php/en/editorial-policies/politics-of-editorials>).

DESCRIPTION OF QUALITY CONTROL SYSTEM (For more detailed information see <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/index.php/en/editorial-policies/the-quality-control-system>).

PLAGIARISM POLICY (For more detailed information see <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/index.php/en/editorial-policies/plagiarism-policy>).

OPEN ACCESS POLICY (For more detailed information see <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/index.php/en/editorial-policies/open-access-statement>).

THE ETHICS CODEX OF SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS (For more detailed information see <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/index.php/en/editorial-policies/the-ethics-codex-of-scientific-publications>).

LICENSE TERMS (For more detailed information see <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org/index.php/en/editorial-policies/license-terms>).

All Manuscripts submitted for publication must go through the review process. Editors read the revised Manuscript. If the Manuscript is improved adequately, it is sent to two (or more) Reviewers for review and to the Statistical Editor, if it contains numerical data. The preliminary evaluation process usually takes 3 weeks.

The Journal is committed to a high standard of editorial ethics.

Editorial Board is used the principles of ethics of scientific publications upon recommendations of International Committee of Medical Journal Editors.

Conflicts of interests of persons who have direct or indirect relation to the publication of the Manuscript or any information containing the Manuscript are settled according to the law of Ukraine in the field of intellectual property.

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENCE ANNALS

SCIENTIFIC EDITION (Journal)
International Journal of Science Annals. 2018

CONTACT INFORMATION

Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH
Kharkiv Regional Public Organization
“Culture of Health”,
Zabaikalskyi lane, 6, of. 6,
Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61105
Tel.: +38 066 239 77 75
Email: ijsa.office@gmail.com
URL: <http://ijsa.culturehealth.org>

Text editing, abstracts translation: Oleksenko O. O.
Managing editor, proof reading: Melnyk Yu. B.
Computer page positioning and layout: Pypenko I. S.
Designer cover: Proskura D. I.
Administrator of site: Stadnik A. V.

passed for printing 30.11.2018
Format A4 (60x90/16)
Paper for multipl. equip. Printed on the risograph.
Conv. printing sheet 2.8. Order № 2-1.1
150 copies.

Publisher
KRPOCH
(Kharkiv Regional Public Organization “Culture of Health”)
Zabaikalskyi lane, 6, of. 6,
Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61105
Tel: +38 066 239 77 75
Email: KhRPOCH@gmail.com
URL: <http://publisher.culturehealth.org>
Certificate to registration
ДК № 4387, 10.08.2012